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**NAVAL
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MONTEREY, CALIFORNIA

THESIS

**THWARTING MONEY LAUNDERING: HOW ARTIFICIAL
INTELLIGENCE CAN ENHANCE FINANCIAL
CRIME ENFORCEMENT**

by

Raymond B. Quinones II

September 2024

Co-Advisors:

Bijan P. Karimi (contractor)
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**THWARTING MONEY LAUNDERING: HOW ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE
CAN ENHANCE FINANCIAL CRIME ENFORCEMENT**

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Submitted in partial fulfillment of the
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ABSTRACT

Artificial intelligence capabilities have increased exponentially in the last decade, affording terrorist and transnational criminal organizations new opportunities to inflict devastating public harm with greater anonymity. The quality of artificially generated text, images, and videos enable greater financial fraud and disinformation. Reactive investigations of these organizations are on the verge of being vastly outpaced by criminal organizations using artificial intelligence. Conversely, artificial intelligence represents a transformative tool for improving national security and delivering superior public services. Since nearly every crime has a financial aspect, prioritizing financial investigations is paramount for thwarting criminals using emerging technology. This thesis explores how U.S. law enforcement can leverage artificial intelligence to enhance transnational money laundering investigations. This study assessed emerging technology implementation by the foreign governments of Estonia and Dubai for best practices. Although Estonia and Dubai effectively introduced emerging technologies, Estonia's higher level of ethical and privacy safeguards reflected its democratic values. This thesis ultimately concluded that U.S. law enforcement should incorporate a centralized digital infrastructure, use commercially available tools, and develop artificial intelligence specific to financial investigations to streamline strategies that will knock down criminal empires.

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LIST OF ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS

AI	artificial intelligence
AML	anti-money laundering
AMLA	Anti-Money Laundering Act
BSA	Bank Secrecy Act
CBP	Customs and Border Protection
CFT	combatting the finance of terrorism
CTR	currency transaction report
DEA	Drug Enforcement Administration
DOJ	Department of Justice
EU	European Union
FATF	Financial Action Task Force
FBI	Federal Bureau of Investigation
FinCEN	Financial Crimes Enforcement Network
FIU	financial intelligence unit
GANs	generative adversarial networks
GAO	Government Accountability Office
HSI	Homeland Security Investigations
IRS-CI	Internal Revenue Service Criminal Investigations
IT	information technology
KYC	know your customer
LLM	large language model
MLO	money laundering organization
OFAC	Office of Foreign Assets Control
P2P	peer to peer
R&D	research and development
RAVEn	Repository for Analytics in a Virtualized Environment
SAR	suspicious activity report
SUA	specified unlawful activity
TBML	trade-based money laundering
TCOs	transnational criminal organizations

UAE	United Arab Emirates
USA PATRIOT	Uniting and Strengthening America by Providing Appropriate Tools Required to Intercept and Obstruct Terrorism
USSS	U.S. Secret Service

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Artificial intelligence (AI) capabilities have increased exponentially in the last decade, affording terrorist and transnational criminal organizations new opportunities to inflict devastating public harm with greater anonymity. Operating in a clandestine environment allows criminal and terrorist organizations to conduct their business unimpeded. Rodrigo Nieto Gomez describes the business environment of transnational criminal organizations (TCO) as operating outside government regulation and only having to consider those regulations when they launder money to bring their illicit proceeds into the regulated economy.¹ In response to law enforcement’s often reactive versus proactive efforts to disrupt and dismantle TCOs, these organizations can rapidly innovate, develop, test, and deploy methods to perpetuate their crimes.² Jennifer Hesterman claims that TCOs and terror groups—at least the best-run, large, and complex ones—use advances in technology, communication, logistics, and globalization to their advantage.³ In the realm of financial crimes, TCOs employ AI to finetune their financial fraud and money laundering capabilities and methods.

The U.S. Department of Homeland Security (DHS) recognizes AI as a transformative tool for enhancing national security, improving operational efficiency, and delivering superior public services. DHS investigative agencies and other law enforcement have begun to integrate AI with its anti-money laundering efforts but need to do more to significantly counter TCOs. This thesis explores how U.S. law enforcement can leverage AI to enhance transnational money laundering investigations. Using the inductive case

¹ Rodrigo Nieto-Gomez, “The Geopolitics of Clandestine Innovation in the Drug Business: A Framework of Analysis to Understand Adaptation Capacities of TCOs,” in *The “New” Face of Transnational Crime Organizations (TCOs): A Geopolitical Perspective and Implications to U.S. National Security*, ed. Ben Riley and Kathleen Kiernan (Washington, DC: Office of the Secretary of Defense, 2013), 152, <https://hdl.handle.net/10945/30346>.

² Nieto-Gomez, 153.

³ Jennifer L. Hesterman, *The Terrorist-Criminal Nexus: An Alliance of International Drug Cartels, Organized Crime, and Terror Groups* (Boca Raton, FL: CRC Press, 2013), 8–9, <https://doi.org/10.1201/b14565>.

study research method, this study assesses emerging technology implementation by the foreign governments of Estonia and Dubai for best practices.⁴

This study looks at the Estonia e-Government for a case study because it is one of the best examples of government adoption of emerging technologies. Likewise, the Dubai AI policy was selected as a case study because it has the most comprehensive adoption of AI than any other foreign law enforcement agency. In the case studies of these foreign implementations of AI, each was evaluated on the same qualitative criteria: effectiveness, cost, privacy, transparency, and accountability.⁵ This thesis highlights the pros and cons of AI use by these governments and examines public concerns for privacy and ethical abuses. It analyzes each case individually and compares those foreign implementations as smart practices, recognizing the limitations of U.S. agencies and recommending a model for law enforcement to improve anti-money laundering investigations.⁶ This comparison not only offers valuable insights into the practical applications of AI in government but also serves as a blueprint for U.S. law enforcement agencies to enhance their capabilities in addressing financial crimes.

The AI strategies of Estonia and Dubai are highly effective. Interestingly, they score differently in the other evaluation categories of cost, privacy, transparency, and accountability. By following different strategies, they quickly developed and incorporated dozens of AI tools to their government services, including their police services. Estonia successfully reduced the necessary costs of AI development by investing with other European countries and using open-source as well as government-owned AI tools. The Estonia X-Road digital backbone simplified integration, whereas Dubai had to invest heavily into digital infrastructure and developed its own AI tools without incorporating many open-source ones. Estonia ranked high for privacy and transparency, whereas Dubai

⁴ Kathleen M. Eisenhardt, “Building Theories from Case Study Research,” *The Academy of Management Review* 14, no. 4 (October 1989): 532, <https://doi.org/10.2307/258557>.

⁵ Eisenhardt, 533.

⁶ Eisenhardt, “Building Theories from Case Study Research”; Eugene Bardach, *A Practical Guide for Policy Analysis: The Eightfold Path to More Effective Problem Solving*, 6th ed. (Thousand Oaks, CA: CQ Press, 2020), 133–44.

ranked low for both categories, notably because it is an authoritarian government. Similarly, Dubai ranked moderate in accountability compared to Estonia's high score.

Although both countries have developed effective AI strategies that enhance public services and governmental operations, Estonia stands out for its strong emphasis on privacy protections, transparency, and ethical accountability. Conversely, Dubai excels in rapid AI deployment and innovative applications, albeit with lower transparency and privacy standards—because of its authoritarian government. These insights demonstrate the importance of a balanced AI strategy that combines robust ethical frameworks with technological innovation. As the United States refines its AI strategy, incorporating the strengths and addressing the weaknesses of Estonia and Dubai's approaches could lead to a more comprehensive and effective AI policy framework.

If harnessed correctly, law enforcement could prevent TCOs and money laundering networks from capitalizing on the benefits AI tools could offer. AI tools should be created and used to highlight weaknesses in the U.S. financial system TCOs are likely to exploit, impede TCOs' ability to register and layer assets through shell companies, actively monitor blockchains for layering of virtual assets, and cross reference disparate data sets. Steps like these would greatly improve law enforcement's effectiveness in countering money laundering.

This thesis recommends three key strategies to amplify the U.S.'s anti-money laundering initiatives against TCOs, which pose serious threats to both national and global financial systems. First, it advocates for the creation of a single digital infrastructure to unify all federal data, enhancing rapid deployment and integration of AI technologies. Second, it proposes fostering mutually beneficial collaboration between the public, private and academic sectors. Third, it recommends a specialized AI policy tailored for DHS law enforcement agencies to advance criminal enforcement and investigations. The final recommendation provides potential tools for the future. These recommendations propose to streamline technology use across government sectors, ensure robust cybersecurity, and improve overall law enforcement effectiveness against complex global crimes.

The research for this thesis reveals a lack of peer reviewed articles on this topic. Further research should examine the adaptive strategies TCOs use to develop and incorporate AI in their money laundering activities. The research should include qualitative analysis of the evolution of AI techniques used by TCOs and quantitative studies on the frequency and success rates of such methods. Similar research should investigate how law enforcement is creating and leveraging AI to make meaningful strides to counter money laundering. Comparative studies across different jurisdictions can provide insights into global best practices in AI application by law enforcement. Research could also explore the development of AI tools and frameworks that can be standardized for cross-border cooperation in money laundering investigations. By expanding the scope to include these areas, future research can map a comprehensive blueprint for effectively managing AI against the sophisticated dynamics of international money laundering.

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I. INTRODUCTION

Operating in a clandestine environment allows criminal and terrorist organizations to conduct their business quickly and without restrictions. Rodrigo Nieto Gomez describes the business environment of transnational criminal organizations (TCOs) as operating outside government regulation and only having to consider those regulations when they launder money to bring their illicit proceeds into the regulated economy.¹ In response to law enforcement’s often reactive versus proactive efforts to disrupt and dismantle TCOs, these organizations can rapidly innovate, develop, test, and deploy methods to perpetuate their crimes.² Jennifer Hesterman claims that TCOs and terror groups—at least the best-run, large, and complex ones—use advances in technology, communication, logistics, and globalization to their advantage.³

Leading up to the terror events of 9/11, for example, Al Qaeda used charitable donations, most notably the Al Haramain Islamic Foundation, to fund their devastating operations.⁴ After law enforcement prosecuted those involved with supporting terrorism through gifts, Al Qaeda and other terrorist organizations began to use the financing methods of TCOs to stay “below the radar.”⁵ This shift in strategy shows the adaptive nature of terrorist organizations and the ongoing challenge for authorities to disrupt their financial networks.

¹ Rodrigo Nieto-Gomez, “The Geopolitics of Clandestine Innovation in the Drug Business: A Framework of Analysis to Understand Adaptation Capacities of TCOs,” in *The “New” Face of Transnational Crime Organizations (TCOs): A Geopolitical Perspective and Implications to U.S. National Security*, ed. Ben Riley and Kathleen Kiernan (Washington, DC: Office of the Secretary of Defense, 2013), 152, <https://hdl.handle.net/10945/30346>.

² Nieto-Gomez, 153.

³ Jennifer L. Hesterman, *The Terrorist-Criminal Nexus: An Alliance of International Drug Cartels, Organized Crime, and Terror Groups* (Boca Raton, FL: CRC Press, 2013), 8–9, <https://doi.org/10.1201/b14565>.

⁴ Christopher M. Blanchard and Alfred B. Prados, *Saudi Arabia: Terrorist Financing Issues*, CRS Report No. RL32499 (Washington, DC: Congressional Research Service, 2007), 19, <https://sgp.fas.org/crs/terror/RL32499.pdf>.

⁵ Hesterman, *The Terrorist-Criminal Nexus*; Mike Schofield, “The Crime-Terror Nexus and the Threat to U.S. Homeland Security” (master’s thesis, Naval Postgraduate School, 2015), <https://hdl.handle.net/10945/47863>.

Understanding these complex financial schemes is crucial for law enforcement. Michael Clements of the U.S. Government Accountability Office (GAO) defines money laundering as, “exploiting vulnerabilities in the global financial system to obscure the source and destination of ill-gotten proceeds and further their illicit activity.”⁶ According to a 2021 GAO report to Congress on money laundering through trade, large professional money laundering networks serve multiple TCOs by moving significant amounts of illicit proceeds worldwide and frequently changing their methods following law enforcement actions such as searches, seizures and arrests.⁷ These large networks span every continent, charge the lowest fees compared to other money laundering networks, and quickly shift operational procedures and tactics as needed.⁸ Law enforcement is having difficulty keeping pace with the continuous adjustments and innovations to launder illicit funds.

A. PROBLEM STATEMENT

Investigations of financial crimes are difficult and time-consuming for several reasons. First, complex money laundering schemes use multiple methods with dozens of bank accounts that each need analysis. Responses from financial institutions take more time for various accounts with numerous months or years of transaction data. Second, before investigators can examine the records, they must convert the information into an organized and adjustable format. After conversion, examiners must check all transaction amounts for accuracy and fix any errors identified. Third, following the money trail leads to other accounts, transactions, and individuals that need investigations, which initiates new data requests and financial analysis. This process can add months or years to an investigation. For example, the Internal Revenue Service (IRS) stated, “Over the course of a four-year investigation, IRS-CI [Criminal Investigations] agents dedicated thousands of

⁶ Michael Clements, *Countering Illicit Finance and Trade: Better Information Sharing and Collaboration Needed to Combat Trade-Based Money Laundering*, GAO-22-447 (Washington, DC: Government Accountability Office, 2021), 1, <https://www.gao.gov/products/gao-22-447>.

⁷ The GAO report highlights a trend of TCOs using Chinese money laundering networks more frequently because they can offer multiple benefits. Clements, *Countering Illicit Finance and Trade*.

⁸ Michael Clements, *Trafficking and Money Laundering: Strategies Used by Criminal Groups and Terrorists and Federal Efforts to Combat Them*, GAO-22-104807 (Washington, DC: Government Accountability Office, 2022), <https://www.gao.gov/products/gao-22-104807>.

hours to unpacking the schemes these perpetrators allegedly facilitated to help their wealthy clients skirt tax obligations.”⁹ Furthermore, law enforcement responds to TCO innovations in the slower, regulated environment that governmental organizations must adhere to. Therefore, law enforcement typically takes years to counter money laundering trends.

But does law enforcement response to TCO money laundering need to take such a long time? Recent technological advancements with artificial intelligence (AI) may be a viable option. Some countries facing comparable challenges have allocated resources to AI and demonstrated some success. Estonia, for example, created a secure electronic government communications system using innovative technology considered revolutionary.¹⁰ The Dubai police implemented a robust AI initiative to develop new techniques to serve the public and increase safety.¹¹ With these adoptions of emerging technologies, my research aims to explore ways U.S. law enforcement can employ AI—specifically natural language processing, machine learning, deep learning, and AI models that use supervised, unsupervised, and hybrid models—to combat money laundering.

B. RESEARCH QUESTION

How can law enforcement use artificial intelligence to enhance money laundering investigations of transnational criminal and terrorist organizations?

C. RESEARCH DESIGN

This thesis aims to answer the question, “How can law enforcement use artificial intelligence to enhance money laundering investigations of transnational criminal organizations and terrorist organizations.” To answer this prescriptive question, this thesis

⁹ Internal Revenue Service, “IRS Spotlights Criminal Investigation Law Enforcement,” Internal Revenue Service, March 18, 2022, <https://www.irs.gov/newsroom/irs-spotlights-criminal-investigation-law-enforcement>.

¹⁰ Jaan Priisalu and Rain Ottis, “Personal Control of Privacy and Data: Estonian Experience,” *Health and Technology* 7, no. 4 (2017): 441–51, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12553-017-0195-1>.

¹¹ Priyankar Bhunia, “Dubai Police Releases 2018–31 Strategic Plan for Artificial Intelligence,” OpenGov Asia, December 21, 2017, <https://opengovasia.com/dubai-police-releases-2018-31-strategic-plan-for-artificial-intelligence/>.

explains how the anti-money laundering methods used by law enforcement today are too slow to dismantle TCOs and Terrorist Organizations effectively. AI can help make that process faster and more effective.

To create replicable research, this thesis uses the inductive case study research method as described by Kathleen Eisenhardt.¹² Eisenhardt describes the iterative process as defining the research question, selecting cases from a specified population, creating protocols for collecting data, analyzing data, shaping hypotheses, comparing literature, and concluding the process when marginal improvement becomes small. She included guidance provided by Robert Yin, who says that case study research design focuses on a logical issue.¹³ He further states that the researcher should review data from outside organizations and logically link it to the subject of research. The inductive case study method is well suited for this thesis because it allows for thorough exploration of complex issues, such as the application of AI in money laundering investigations. This framework is advantageous over simply deductive or quantitative approaches because it provides the flexibility needed to generate theory from real-world data, giving a clearer understanding of how AI can improve law enforcement methods. Additionally, Eisenhardt's iterative approach ensures emerging insights are integrated, which leads to robust and actionable conclusions.

This thesis utilizes peer-reviewed journal articles, academic books, government documents, and court reports as primary sources. The search terms used include “artificial intelligence,” “machine learning,” “large language model,” “deep learning,” “financial crime,” “money laundering,” “government,” and “law enforcement.” This research uses several definitions specific to artificial intelligence relevant to money laundering and criminal investigations. Those definitions include:

¹² Kathleen M. Eisenhardt, “Building Theories from Case Study Research,” *The Academy of Management Review* 14, no. 4 (October 1989): 532, <https://doi.org/10.2307/258557>.

¹³ Robert K. Yin, *Case Study Research and Applications: Design and Methods*, 6th ed. (Thousand Oaks, CA: SAGE Publications, Inc., 2018), 25–26.

- Machine Learning: A subset of artificial intelligence with algorithms that make decisions based on previous experience or input.¹⁴
- Natural Language Processing: A field of computer science where computers use language models to analyze and understand human language by anticipating the likelihood of different language expressions.¹⁵
- Neural Networks: Machine learning that uses nodes that mimic brain structure and function. Outputs of one element, or node, are inputs to others. These nodes receive and send outputs to and from different layers until the last output is created based on the training procedures paired with very large data.¹⁶
- Deep Learning: Using neural networks, learns complex functions by transforming raw input through multiple layers of simple, non-linear modules. Each layer provides a more abstract representation of the data.¹⁷
- Supervised: Machine learning that uses pre-defined data to result in a known outcome with the intention to teach a machine how to operate.¹⁸
- Unsupervised: Machine learning that uses non-pre-defined data to result in an outcome based on the data and analysis structure. The outcome is not previously known.¹⁹

¹⁴ John Beccia, Imad Habre, and Max Lerner, “Integrating AI, Machine Learning and Robotics into Legacy AFC Systems,” ACAMS, June 8, 2020, <https://lms.acams.org/myCatalog/3189/1380744>.

¹⁵ Stuart J. Russell, Peter Norvig, and Ernest Davis, *Artificial Intelligence: A Modern Approach*, 3rd ed. (Upper Saddle River, NJ: Prentice Hall, 2010), 860.

¹⁶ Nils J. Nilsson, *The Quest for Artificial Intelligence: A History of Ideas and Achievements* (Cambridge, UK: Cambridge University Press, 2010), 64–67.

¹⁷ Yann LeCun, Yoshua Bengio, and Geoffrey Hinton, “Deep Learning,” *Nature* 521, no. 7553 (May 28, 2015): 436, <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature14539>.

¹⁸ Beccia, Habre, and Lerner, “Integrating AI, Machine Learning.”

¹⁹ Beccia, Habre, and Lerner.

- Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs): Deep learning models with a generator that uses a rapid, iterative training process to create realistic outputs so that a discriminator can't differentiate between real and generated data. Through the training process, the generate improves at making realistic outputs while the discriminator improves at telling fake from real outputs. The two networks compete against each other in an adversarial manner.²⁰
- Deepfakes: Video or audio production of false content using GANs²¹

This thesis employs case studies of two foreign implementations of AI and evaluates each on the same qualitative criteria: effectiveness, cost, privacy, transparency, and accountability.²² The case studies address government implementation of emerging technology.²³ This study looks at the Estonia e-Government for a case study because it is one of the best examples of government adoption of emerging technologies. Likewise, the Dubai AI policy was selected as a case study because it has the most comprehensive adoption of AI than any other foreign law enforcement agency. This thesis highlights the pros and cons of AI use by governments and examines public concerns for privacy and ethical abuses. Finally, this thesis analyzes each case individually and then compares those foreign implementations as smart practices, recognizing the limitations of U.S. agencies and recommending a model for law enforcement to improve anti-money laundering investigations.²⁴

²⁰ Ricardo Ribeiro Pereira, "A Machine Learning Approach to Money Laundering Detection Inspired by GANs" (master's thesis, Universidade do Porto (Portugal), 2021), ProQuest.

²¹ Anna Broinowski, "Deepfake Nightmares, Synthetic Dreams: A Review of Dystopian and Utopian Discourses Around Deepfakes, and Why the Collapse of Reality May Not Be Imminent—Yet," *Journal of Asia-Pacific Pop Culture* 7, no. 1 (2022): 110, <https://muse.jhu.edu/pub/2/article/857647>.

²² Eisenhardt, "Building Theories from Case Study Research," 533.

²³ Yin, *Case Study Research and Applications*, 31.

²⁴ Eisenhardt, "Building Theories from Case Study Research"; Eugene Bardach, *A Practical Guide for Policy Analysis: The Eightfold Path to More Effective Problem Solving*, 6th ed. (Thousand Oaks, CA: CQ Press, 2020), 133–44.

II. BACKGROUND ON ANTI-MONEY LAUNDERING

This chapter lays out a historical context and overview of current money laundering methods and techniques law enforcement employs to investigate financial crimes. It explains how criminal entities use various methods to hide the source of their illegal proceeds from and avoid alerting law enforcement. The chapter then details the legal framework created to hinder a criminal organization's ability to access proceeds from criminal activities for personal enrichment or to further criminal activities. Finally, the chapter ends with an exploration of what law enforcement traditionally does to investigate money laundering activities, followed by a brief introduction to new artificial intelligence capabilities. This foundation allows the reader to understand how AI may enhance anti-money laundering processes. This chapter demonstrates that law enforcement's anti-money laundering techniques are outmatched by the agility and innovativeness of TCOs in money laundering.

A. TCO MONEY LAUNDERING METHODS

Transnational criminal organizations use different techniques to expend their ill-gotten gains, but all have the same three stages. The three stages of money laundering are placement, layering and integration. In the placement stage, illicit proceeds enter a financial institution. During the layering stage, the funds are moved to conceal the illicit origin. In the final stage of integration, the apparently legitimate funds are used to purchase assets or investments.²⁵ Some TCOs have used more complicated methods than others, but all have incorporated these basic stages. Figure 1 illustrates how illicit proceeds move through the different stages of money laundering.

²⁵ Nicholas Gilmour, "Illustrating the Incentivised Steps Criminals Take to Launder Cash While Avoiding Government Anti-Laundering Measures," *Journal of Money Laundering Control* 23, no. 2 (2020): 515, <https://doi.org/10.1108/JMLC-12-2019-0095>.

Figure 1. Stages of Money Laundering²⁶

According to Figure 1, illicit proceeds enter a financial institution in the Placement stage, transfer through multiple accounts in the Layering stage, and are finally used to purchase assets in the Integration stage. This portion of the chapter will review common money laundering methods with accompanying case examples. A summary explaining where each of those methods are used in the money laundering stages are below.

1. Structuring

A simple method to place proceeds of illegal activity into the formal banking system while hiding identities of the individuals depositing cash is “structuring.” The Bank Secrecy Act (BSA) required financial institutions to file Currency Transaction Reports (CTRs). Whenever a person or business deposits or withdraws cash in the amount of \$10,000 or greater, a CTR must be filed.²⁷ When a CTR is filed, identifying information of the account owner and person conducting the transaction are provided.²⁸ TCOs often break up cash into multiple amounts below \$10,000 and deposit them into bank accounts to avoid the CTR reporting requirement. This pattern of deposit activity is known as

²⁶ Adapted from Gilmour, “Illustrating the Incentivised Steps.”

²⁷ The Bank Secrecy Act of 1970, Pub. L. 91–508, 84 Stat. 1114.

²⁸ The Bank Secrecy Act of 1970.

“structuring,” as defined by the United States Code of Federal Regulations.²⁹ TCOs will use very low level members or pay individuals who are not part of the organization to make the structured deposits. Operating in this manner helps distance the upper level criminals from the currency transactions and provides some protection from law enforcement detection

For example, Raul Mendoza, owner of a car dealership, and his accomplices conspired to structure cash deposits with the intent to evade lawful reporting requirements. According to the Department of Justice (DOJ) press release, an investigation by Homeland Security Investigations (HSI), the Drug Enforcement Administration (DEA), and the Internal Revenue Service Criminal Investigations (IRS-CI) concluded daily cash receipts from Chopeque Auto Sales were “structured into separate accounts at various banks to avoid the \$10,000 reporting requirements.”³⁰ They structured over 700 deposits totaling \$4,543,714 during a four-year period.³¹

2. Shell Companies

To assist with placement and obfuscation of funds, TCOs use shell companies. Shell companies are legal entities that can engage in contracts and own property while not having a physical location, but rather only a mailing address to receive correspondence.³² TCOs will often use third parties to open shell companies and associated bank accounts without using any information that would link the shell company to the beneficial owner. By hiding the true ownership and using a legal corporate entity, risk to the TCO is minimized. TCOs are then able to use the shell companies to receive and transfer vast

²⁹ General Provisions, 31 C.F.R. 1010, (2024), <https://www.ecfr.gov/current/title-31/subtitle-B/chapter-X/part-1010>.

³⁰ “Owner of Colorado Car Dealership Sentenced for Structuring and Money Laundering,” U.S. Attorney’s Office, District of Colorado, December 1, 2015, <https://www.justice.gov/usao-co/pr/owner-colorado-car-dealership-sentenced-structuring-and-money-laundering>.

³¹ U.S. Attorney’s Office, District of Colorado.

³² Ola M. Tucker, *The Flow of Illicit Funds: A Case Study Approach to Anti-Money Laundering Compliance* (Washington, DC: Georgetown University Press, 2022), 33, <https://doi.org/10.2307/j.ctv2m2fv8m>.

amount of illicit funds throughout the globe.³³ Drug dealers, terrorists, fraudsters, money launderers and corrupt officials often use shell companies.³⁴ According to a World Bank study of over 200 largescale corruption cases, “70 percent of the cases relied on anonymous companies to hide gains from corruption.”³⁵ The use of shell companies is a relatively simple way for TCOs and money laundering organizations (MLOs) to make transactions of illicit proceeds appear legitimate while obscuring the true ownership and source of funds.

A prime example of a shell company being used to conceal beneficial ownership of a corrupt official is that of Gulnara Karimova. Ms. Karimova is the daughter of Islam Karimov, former president of Uzbekistan.³⁶ After the collapse of the Soviet Union in 1991, Karimov became president and maintained a closed economy.³⁷ According to the DOJ press release, Ms. Karimova used her status for personal gain while her father was president. The U.S. indictment alleges that she received over \$865 million in bribes from three telecommunication companies in exchange for her influence over the Uzbekistan telecom regulator.³⁸ The telecom companies entered into agreements to pay consulting fees to Karimova’s shell companies that had neither the ability nor expertise to provide the contracted services.³⁹ Payments were concealed through various shell companies that were beneficially owned by Karimova. The funds were transmitted through financial institutions through New York City to accounts controlled by Karimova in other parts of the world,

³³ Tucker, 34–35.

³⁴ Carl Pacini et al., “The Role of Shell Entities in Fraud and Other Financial Crimes,” *Managerial Auditing Journal* 34, no. 3 (2019): 247–67, <https://doi.org/10.1108/MAJ-01-2018-1768>.

³⁵ “Anonymous Companies: A Global Witness Briefing,” Global Witness, May 10, 2013, <https://en/archive/anonymous-companies-global-witness-briefing/>.

³⁶ “Former Uzbek Government Official and Uzbek Telecommunications Executive Charged in Bribery and Money Laundering Scheme Involving the Payment of Nearly \$1 Billion in Bribes,” U.S. Attorney’s Office, Southern District of New York, March 7, 2019, <https://www.justice.gov/usao-sdny/pr/former-uzbek-government-official-and-uzbek-telecommunications-executive-charged-bribery>.

³⁷ *Britannica*, s.v. “Economy of Uzbekistan,” accessed July 3, 2023, <https://www.britannica.com/place/Uzbekistan/Economy>.

³⁸ U.S. Attorney’s Office, Southern District of New York, “Former Uzbek Government Official.”

³⁹ “SDNY CM/ECF NextGen Version 1.6,” accessed July 3, 2023, <https://ecf.nysd.uscourts.gov/doc1/127124311007>.

including Ireland, the United Kingdom, France, Belgium, Luxembourg, Switzerland, Austria, the Netherlands, Norway, Sweden, Latvia, and Cyprus.⁴⁰ As a result of the HSI, IRS-CI and DOJ investigation, Karimova was arrested by the government of Uzbekistan and placed in house arrest. Luxury properties and assets purchased with her bribe proceeds were seized by governments around the world.⁴¹ Three telecom companies entered into deferred prosecution agreements with the DOJ and were fined a combined total of \$2.61 billion.⁴²

3. Funnel Accounts

Another commonly used tactic for TCOs to launder proceeds across borders is the use of funnel accounts. According to the Financial Crimes Enforcement Network (FinCEN), a funnel account is an “individual or business account in one geographic area that receives multiple cash deposits, often in amounts below the cash reporting threshold, and from which the funds are withdrawn in a different geographic area with little time elapsing between the deposits and withdrawals.”⁴³ In some instances the account holder’s profession, as stated on the account, does not match the deposit and withdrawal activity, which may occur thousands of miles apart for no seemingly legitimate reason.⁴⁴ Deposits to a single account from multiple geographic locations followed by withdrawals from a single and significantly different location spiked in the United States soon after Mexico implemented new anti-money laundering (AML) regulations in 2010 that greatly limited U.S. dollar deposits in banks as well as U.S. dollar transactions outside of the banking system. The regulations limited conversion of dollars to pesos to \$4,000 per month and stipulated that transactions outside of banks non-account holders could only exchange up

⁴⁰ U.S. Attorney’s Office, Southern District of New York, “Former Uzbek Government Official.”

⁴¹ Andy Verity, “Gulnara Karimova: How Uzbek President’s Daughter Built a £200m Property Empire,” BBC News, March 13, 2023, <https://www.bbc.com/news/world-64915348>.

⁴² U.S. Attorney’s Office, Southern District of New York, “Former Uzbek Government Official.”

⁴³ Financial Crimes Enforcement Network, “Update on U.S. Currency Restrictions in Mexico: Funnel Accounts and TBML,” FIN-2014-A005 (Washington, DC: Department of the Treasury, May 28, 2014), <https://www.fincen.gov/resources/advisories/fincen-advisory-fin-2014-a005>.

⁴⁴ Financial Crimes Enforcement Network, “Information on Narcotics and Bulk Currency Corridors,” FIN-2011-A009 (Washington, DC: Department of the Treasury, April 21, 2011), <https://www.fincen.gov/resources/advisories/fincen-advisory-fin-2011-a009>.

to \$300 per day and no more than \$1,500 per month.⁴⁵ Understanding the mechanics of funnel accounts and their rise following regulatory changes is crucial for developing more effective countermeasures against international money laundering activities.

After Mexico enacted its 2010 AML regulations, Mexican-based money laundering organizations adjusted how they laundered cash proceeds through their previously established currency exchange networks. For instance, Cesar Hernandez-Martinez owned a currency exchange house in Tijuana, Mexico and offered his services to Joaquin “El Chapo” Guzman’s Sinaloa Cartel. Hernandez-Martinez and his accomplices would receive cash proceeds from the sale of cocaine, methamphetamines and heroin, in the form of U.S. dollars, that were smuggled from the United States to Mexico.⁴⁶ Instead of conducting exchanges of U.S. dollars to Mexican pesos in Mexico, like they had in the past, the Hernandez-Martinez MLO moved U.S. dollars from Mexico to the United States with Mexican armored car services.⁴⁷ The armored car services filed false reports to the U.S. FinCEN regarding the international transportation of currency or monetary instruments. After entering the United States, the multiple armored cars transferred millions of dollars of cash per load to various locations from southwestern states to Midwest states until the cash was eventually deposited into a funnel account appearing to have been derived from legal activity that used a legitimate armored car service. Once the funds were deposited in the U.S. funnel account, the MLO wired the funds to a Mexico bank account controlled by the MLO. A Mexican armored car service would then bring Mexican pesos from the bank to the currency exchange businesses that had originally received the U.S. dollars. This entire process would occur within 24 hours.⁴⁸ Cesar Hernandez-Martinez and five other

⁴⁵ Carlos Navarro, “Government Imposes Tight Restrictions on Cash Transactions to Reduce Laundering Drug Profits” (SourceMex, August 4, 2010), <https://digitalrepository.unm.edu/sourcemex/5423>.

⁴⁶ U.S. Immigration and Customs Enforcement, “Tijuana Currency Exchange House Owner Sentenced to 137 Months for Laundering \$13 Million of Narcotics Proceeds for Sinaloa Cartel,” U.S. Immigration and Customs Enforcement, February 4, 2020, <https://www.ice.gov/news/releases/tijuana-currency-exchange-house-owner-sentenced-137-months-laundering-13-million>.

⁴⁷ U.S. District Court, Southern District of California, “USA v Omar AyonDiaz et al. Indictment,” December 4, 2015, https://ecf.casd.uscourts.gov/cgi-bin/show_temp.pl?file=9530785-0--68060.pdf&type=application/pdf.

⁴⁸ Gary Tirabassi, “HSI Sinaloa ML Case Review.”

main conspirators of the MLO were arrested by HSI and pled guilty to Conspiracy to Commit International Money Laundering in violation of Title 18 United States Code 1956(a)(2)(B)(i). They were subsequently sentenced to serve between 96 to 137 months in federal prison and forfeited millions of dollars in proceeds.⁴⁹

Funnel accounts were also used by Ricardo Valenzuela-Gale, who ran a different MLO with ties to the Sinaloa Cartel and Jalisco New Generation Cartel in Mexico. An investigation by HSI, DEA and IRS-CI found that Valenzuela-Gale’s MLO laundered over \$32 million from the sale of narcotics, including fentanyl.⁵⁰ Members of the MLO located in numerous places throughout the U.S. received narcotics proceeds in cash. They communicated on anonymous prepaid phones with photographs and code phrases to coordinate bulk currency deposits into funnel bank accounts. After the funds were deposited into the funnel accounts, the money was wired to personal bank accounts in Mexico where it was later provided to the drug cartels.⁵¹ Many of the MLO members arrested have plead guilty to Conspiracy to Launder Monetary Instruments in violation of Title 18 United States Code Section 1956(h) and were sentenced to serve time in prison.⁵²

4. Informal Value Transfer Systems

The smuggling of illicit goods and people by TCOs from one part of the world to another require the exchange of currencies so TCO members at the origin and transit locations can be paid in a currency that can be used in the country they reside in rather than in the currency of the end user location. Therefore, currency exchange networks are commonly used, as illustrated in the previous example with armored car services and

⁴⁹ “3:15-Cr-00950-BEN USA v. Ayon-Diaz et Al.; U.S. Immigration and Customs Enforcement, “Tijuana Currency Exchange House Owner Sentenced”; U.S. Attorney’s Office, Southern District of California, “Sinaloa Cartel Drug Trafficker and Money Launderer Sentenced to More than 13 Years in Prison,” U.S. Attorney’s Office, Southern District of California, October 14, 2020, <https://www.justice.gov/usao-sdca/pr/sinaloa-cartel-drug-trafficker-and-money-launderer-sentenced-more-13-years-prison>; and Tirabassi, “HSI Sinaloa ML Case Review.”

⁵⁰ “Alleged Money Launderers for Mexican Cartels Indicted,” U.S. Attorney’s Office, Southern District of California, November 16, 2021, <https://www.justice.gov/usao-sdca/pr/alleged-money-launderers-mexican-cartels-indicted>.

⁵¹ U.S. Attorney’s Office, Southern District of California.

⁵² “Case Summary 3:21-Cr-02546-GPC USA v. Valenzuela-Gale, et Al.”; 3:21-cr-02546-GPC-4,7,10,14,15,17,20,24,25,28,29,30,32 USA v. Valenzuela-Gale et al.

funnel accounts. But there are fewer formal exchanges that are also exploited by criminals. A study by Teichmann and Falker revealed specific information on how informal value transfer systems, also known as hawala networks, were used by TCOs as a form of underground currency exchanges.⁵³ While conducting their research, Teichmann and Falker interviewed “42 alleged money launderers, their associates and 18 compliance officers.”⁵⁴ The study identified three key points:

1. Exchange of amounts less than \$100 million can be conducted fairly easily for TCOs
2. Exchange of large amounts over \$100 million are more difficult and typically require a corrupt central bank official to assist
3. The safest means of transacting money exchanges is through an informal value transfer system, commonly referred to as a hawala, where funds are not moved from one country to another but “only the difference between two amounts is transferred.”⁵⁵

One of their interviewees provided an example of a Latvian in London who wanted to send illicit proceeds in the form of euros to Latvia and a different person in Latvia wanted to send money to Great Britain in the form of pounds. In this example, two people acting as brokers in both London and Latvia receive and give money to counterparts in their respective countries without sending any funds across borders. Informal value transfer systems were originally used for legitimate purposes like providing money to family members in their home country, but it is easily exploited by TCOs for money laundering obfuscation.⁵⁶ The informal value transfer system insulates TCOs by conducting much less

⁵³ Fabian Maximilian Teichmann and Marie-Christin Falker, “Money Laundering via Underground Currency Exchange Networks,” *Journal of Financial Regulation and Compliance* 29, no. 1 (2021): 1–2, <https://doi.org/10.1108/JFRC-01-2020-0003>.

⁵⁴ Teichmann and Falker, 2.

⁵⁵ Teichmann and Falker, 8–10.

⁵⁶ Financial Crimes Enforcement Network, “FinCEN Issues Report on Informal Value Transfer Systems” (Washington, DC: Department of the Treasury, November 22, 2002), <https://www.fincen.gov/news/news-releases/fincen-issues-report-informal-value-transfer-systems>.

traceable money movements.⁵⁷ It is important for law enforcement to be aware of informal value transfer systems when investigating the financial activity of TCOs, otherwise they might not notice how funds are being transferred.

Iranian businesses used an informal value transfer system to move funds from Iran to the United States for investment in violation of the Iran Trade Embargo. Consider the case of Mahmoud Reza Banki, a former management consultant and U.S. citizen living in Manhattan. He illegally received approximately \$3.4 million into his New York bank account from individuals in the United States and other countries. The transfers were arranged by Banki's father and hawala operators in Iran. Banki's father paid millions of dollars' worth of Iranian currency (Tomans) to hawala operators. The hawala operators based in Iran coordinated with hawala operators in the U.S. to transfer the value of Tomans in U.S. dollars to Banki's bank account.⁵⁸ The U.S. dollars transferred into Banki's bank account originated from individuals and businesses seeking to send money to Iran, circumventing the Iran Trade Embargo. Profits for hawala operators came from exploiting fluctuations in the dollar to Toman exchange rate, while Banki used substantial funds deposited into his account for personal enrichment and real estate investments.⁵⁹ The Office of Foreign Assets Control (OFAC) is the agency within the U.S. Department of Treasury responsible for enforcement of Iran Trade Embargo and other sanctions.⁶⁰ The investigation by HSI and OFAC led to Banki's arrest and conviction for "violating the Iran Trade Embargo and operating an unlicensed money transfer business between the United States and Iran."⁶¹

⁵⁷ Teichmann and Falker, "Money Laundering via Underground Currency," 9–10.

⁵⁸ U.S. Attorney's Office, Southern District of New York, "Former Management Consultant Sentenced in Manhattan Federal Court to 30 Months in Prison for Criminal Violations of Iran Trade Embargo, Unlicensed Money Transmitting, and False Statements" (New York: U.S. Attorney's Office, Southern District of New York, August 16, 2010), <https://www.justice.gov/archive/usao/nys/pressreleases/August10/bankimahmoudrezasentencingpr.pdf>.

⁵⁹ U.S. Attorney's Office, Southern District of New York.

⁶⁰ *Restrictions on International Travel: Hearing before Committee on Foreign Affairs, Subcommittee on International Economic Policy and Trade, House of Representatives*, 101st Cong., 2 (1990), ProQuest.

⁶¹ U.S. Attorney's Office, Southern District of New York, "Former Management Consultant Sentenced."

In another example, Yossi Avitan, Ori Saadon and four other individuals operated an informal value transfer system in furtherance of various financial fraud schemes that caused victims to lose more than \$13 million.⁶² Saadon is an Israeli national who lived in Israel during the time of the criminal activity. Avitan and the four other co-conspirators were Israeli nationals who lived in the United States. The co-conspirators operated in the United States, Europe and Israel. The investigators gained some of their evidence by providing undercover funds to the MLO and observing the value transfer among various locations.⁶³ Avitan and others made efforts to conceal their money transmitting activity from U.S. law enforcement and government regulators by making anonymous arrangements for monetary transactions, conducting monetary transactions on the street, accepting and delivering cash without corresponding documentation and failing to file CTRs.⁶⁴ In 2016, the Federal Bureau of Investigation (FBI), U.S. Department of the Treasury Office of Inspector General with assistance from HSI, U.S. Secret Service (USSS), and the U.S. Department of State Diplomatic Security Service (DSS) arrested Avitan, Saadon and the other conspirators who pled guilty.

5. Trade-based Money Laundering

Another common method for TCOs to launder illicit proceeds and move value is through international trade transactions to legitimate the illicit origins or hide the intent to facilitate criminal activity.⁶⁵ This laundering method is referred to as trade-based money laundering. TCOs direct their criminal proceeds to purchase merchandise which is then shipped to countries where the criminal activity or illicit goods originated.⁶⁶ Colombian drug cartels will use money brokers as intermediaries to coordinate the purchase of

⁶² “19 People Indicted Following Investigations into International Fraud and Money Laundering Rings,” U.S. Attorney’s Office, District of Columbia, March 1, 2017, <https://www.justice.gov/usao-dc/pr/19-people-indicted-following-investigations-international-fraud-and-money-laundering>.

⁶³ USA v GAJDOS et al. History Documents; USA v GAJDOS et al. Indictment.

⁶⁴ 1:17-Cr-00017-CKK USA v. AVITAN et Al.

⁶⁵ Financial Action Task Force, *Trade-Based Money Laundering* (Paris: Financial Action Task Force, 2006), <https://www.fatf-gafi.org/en/publications/Methodsand Trends/Trade-basedmoneylaundering.html>.

⁶⁶ Department of the Treasury, *National Money Laundering Risk Assessment* (Washington, DC: Department of the Treasury, 2022), 14, 22.

merchandise in the United States, paid for with U.S. currency drug proceeds, which is then sent to Colombia. After the merchandise arrives in Colombia, the broker pays the drug cartel in the form of pesos. This use of unregulated money exchangers is known as the Black Market Peso Exchange.⁶⁷ Colombian drug cartels developed this form of trade-based money laundering commonly used across Latin America in the Black Market Peso Exchange.

Trade-based money laundering (TBML) can also be done through over- and under-invoicing of goods and services.⁶⁸ Exporters and importers misrepresent the value of goods to facilitate the transfer of value or settle debts among the parties involved in the trade.⁶⁹ Cassara provides a simple example of under- and over-invoicing:

Company A located in the United States ships one million widgets worth \$2 each to Company B based in Mexico. On the invoice, however, Company A lists the widgets at a price of only \$1 each, and the Mexican importer pays the U.S. exporter only \$1 million for them. Thus, extra value has been transferred to Mexico, where the importer can sell (directly or indirectly) the widgets on the open market for a total of \$2 million. The Mexican company ...[may] transfer [the profits] to a criminal organization that may be the power behind the business transactions. To transfer value in the opposite direction, an exporter can over-invoice goods above their fair market price. In this manner, the exporter receives value from the importer because the latter's payment is higher than the goods' actual value on the open market.⁷⁰

The TBML scheme can be further exemplified by the case involving Si Oh Rhew and Lance Rhew who owned C'est Toi Jean, Inc., in the Los Angeles Fashion District. They purchased garments from overseas manufacturers, including China, and provided false invoices to Customs and Border Protection (CBP) that undervalued the items being imported by over \$62 million, subsequently helping them avoid paying tariffs of \$10.3

⁶⁷ Department of the Treasury, 22.

⁶⁸ Financial Action Task Force, *Trade-Based Money Laundering*.

⁶⁹ John A. Cassara and Chip Poncy, *Trade-Based Money Laundering: The Next Frontier in International Money Laundering Enforcement* (Hoboken, NJ: John Wiley & Sons, 2015), 16, ProQuest Ebook Central.

⁷⁰ Cassara and Poncy, 16–17.

million.⁷¹ A large-scale investigation led by HSI with the assistance of IRS-CI, CBP and local police departments revealed significant Black Market Peso Exchange schemes as well as the under-invoicing scheme. Si Oh and Lance Rhew received millions of dollars in bulk U.S. currency from Mexican drug cartels paying for clothes and other items in furtherance of their money laundering schemes. They failed to file any CTRs even though they received multiple payments over \$10,000 in cash, and they filed fraudulent tax returns to the IRS that omitted over \$17.6 million in gross sales.⁷²

Sang Bum Noh, owner of Ambiance Apparel, is another individual charged in the L.A. Fashion District case. Ambiance Apparel, like C'est Toi Jeans, Inc., undervalued goods being imported and failed to file CTRs. The business used two sets of books to records sales to hide cash transactions.⁷³ According to the DOJ press release, after HSI arrested Noh, he pled guilty to money laundering and customs offenses, was sentenced to one year in prison followed by “five years’ probation and ordered to implement an anti-money laundering” and ethics program and pay nearly \$118 million.⁷⁴

6. Peer to Peer (P2P) Transfer Services

The use of peer to peer (P2P) transfer systems like Zelle and CashApp has grown.⁷⁵ While these types of digital payments have expedited the movement of money among friends or between a buyer and seller without needing to use cash, criminals are taking advantage of the underregulated platforms.⁷⁶ P2P transfer systems serve as third-party

⁷¹ “Fashion District Wholesaler and 2 Men Linked to Company Indicted in Schemes to Avoid Tariffs, Launder Drug Money and Avoid Taxes,” U.S. Attorney’s Office, Central District of California, December 10, 2020, <https://www.justice.gov/usao-cdca/pr/fashion-district-wholesaler-and-2-men-linked-company-indicted-schemes-avoid-tariffs>.

⁷² U.S. Attorney’s Office, Central District of California.

⁷³ “Los Angeles Fashion District Company Owner Sentenced to One Year in Prison for Committing Customs Violations and Tax Offenses,” U.S. Attorney’s Office, Central District of California, December 6, 2021, <https://www.justice.gov/usao-cdca/pr/los-angeles-fashion-district-company-owner-sentenced-one-year-prison-committing-customs>.

⁷⁴ U.S. Attorney’s Office, Central District of California.

⁷⁵ Daniel Bethencourt, “Fraudsters Channeling Funds Through Fintech Firms: Sources,” Money Laundering, June 16, 2020, accessed July 11, 2023, <https://www.moneylaundering.com/news/fraudsters-channeling-funds-through-fintech-firms-sources/>.

⁷⁶ Bethencourt.

payment services among individuals, businesses and banks.⁷⁷ Customer identities are often not disclosed and it is easy for KYC screening to be circumvented by using false names.⁷⁸ Money launderers see P2Ps as an easy means to layer illicit funds due to the timeliness of each transaction that allows for multiple transactions to occur rapidly in order to complicate the fund flows and hide the suspicious activity among large volumes of data produced.⁷⁹ Although the amounts associated with P2P transfers are relatively low, they should not be overlooked by law enforcement as they can support evidence of laundering illicit proceeds derived from crimes like drug trafficking and financial fraud.

7. Virtual Assets

A newer form of P2P money laundering for TCOs is through the use of virtual assets like Bitcoin. Virtual assets often use cryptographic technology to conduct secure transactions through distributed ledger technology, known as a “blockchain,” which is available on a public network.⁸⁰ Virtual assets is a broad term that includes anything that is created on or exchanged on a blockchain.⁸¹ They include crypto assets, stablecoins, non-fungible tokens (NFTs), and security tokens.⁸² Crypto assets are any digital store of value stored on a blockchain.⁸³ Stablecoins tie their value to an external reference, like a reserve of fiat currency.⁸⁴ NFTs are tokens that represent ownership of a unique digital item, like art, and the holder of the NFT is the owner of the digital asset.⁸⁵ Security tokens represent

⁷⁷ Lin Danwan, “Common Money Laundering Risks with Third-Party Payments,” ACFE Insights, March 26, 2021, <https://www.acfeinsights.com/acfe-insights/money-laundering-risks-third-party-payments>.

⁷⁸ Danwan.

⁷⁹ Danwan.

⁸⁰ Nadine Schwarz et al., *Virtual Assets and Anti-Money Laundering and Combating the Financing of Terrorism (1): Some Legal and Practical Considerations* (Washington, DC: International Monetary Fund, 2021), <https://www.imf.org/en/Publications/fintech-notes/Issues/2021/10/14/Virtual-Assets-and-Anti-Money-Laundering-and-Combating-the-Financing-of-Terrorism-1-463654>.

⁸¹ “Demystifying Cryptocurrency and Digital Assets,” PwC Tech Effect, accessed July 10, 2023, <https://www.pwc.com/us/en/tech-effect/emerging-tech/understanding-cryptocurrency-digital-assets.html>.

⁸² PwC.

⁸³ PwC.

⁸⁴ PwC.

⁸⁵ PwC.

ownership of something on the blockchain, like a share of the company issuing the token, and are considered securities or financial investments by regulatory agencies.⁸⁶ Recognizing the use of virtual assets by TCOs for money laundering underscores the necessity for regulatory frameworks to evolve in tandem with these technologies to mitigate the risk of financial crimes in the digital age.

The most well-known crypto asset is Bitcoin. Bitcoin was the first type of virtual asset to use the blockchain when it was created in 2009 as a form of decentralized currency that operates apart from formal institutions and fiat currencies, government issued legal tender.⁸⁷ Crypto assets, like Bitcoin, Ethereum, and Tether, gained notoriety in their early years because they were used almost exclusively on darknet marketplaces for criminal transactions including drug sales, child exploitation, and gun sales.⁸⁸ The darknet is non-indexed web content consisting of multiple networks on the internet that can only be accessed with certain software that is configured to provide anonymity.⁸⁹ So much Bitcoin was used on the Silk Road darknet marketplace, that it drew the attention of hackers and thieves. James Zhong stole over 50,000 Bitcoin from the marketplace through fraud by creating multiple Silk Road accounts to hide his identity and then initiated more than 140 transactions in rapid succession that caused the marketplace platform send him Bitcoin in error after being overwhelmed.⁹⁰ Although crypto assets gained notoriety on the darknet, they are becoming more mainstream and accepted.

⁸⁶ PwC; and Brian Nibley, “What Is a Security Token in Crypto? How Do They Work?,” SoFi, December 5, 2021, <https://www.sofi.com/learn/content/security-tokens-cryptocurrency/>.

⁸⁷ Schwarz et al., *Virtual Assets and Anti-Money Laundering*; Aljosha Judmayer et al., *Blocks and Chains: Introduction to Bitcoin, Cryptocurrencies, and Their Consensus Mechanisms* (Cham, Switzerland: Springer International Publishing, 2017), 2, ProQuest Ebook Central; and Debra Amato, “Understanding Crypto vs. Fiat Currency,” *California Business Journal*, accessed July 11, 2023, <https://calbizjournal.com/understanding-crypto-vs-fiat-currency/>.

⁸⁸ “A Primer on DarkNet Marketplaces,” Federal Bureau of Investigation News Stories, November 1, 2016, <https://www.fbi.gov/news/stories/a-primer-on-darknet-marketplaces>.

⁸⁹ Federal Bureau of Investigation.

⁹⁰ “U.S. Attorney Announces Historic \$3.36 Billion Cryptocurrency Seizure and Conviction in Connection with Silk Road Dark Web Fraud,” U.S. Attorney’s Office, Southern District of New York, November 7, 2022, <https://www.justice.gov/usao-sdny/pr/us-attorney-announces-historic-336-billion-cryptocurrency-seizure-and-conviction>.

The stigma associated with Bitcoin and other crypto assets from their use on the darknet has been replaced by excitement over great investment opportunities they can present. As of July 11, 2023, there are over 26,000 crypto assets, or “cryptocurrencies,” in existence.⁹¹ The value of Bitcoin increased from fractions of a penny in 2009 to almost \$69,000 at its highest point in November 2021.⁹² Celebrities like Bill Gates, Madonna, Lionel Messi and Gwyneth Paltrow invested in crypto assets and endorsed related products.⁹³ Bitcoin and other crypto assets will continue to be used by TCOs and money laundering networks because so much money can be transferred throughout the world so rapidly compared to other methods, especially as more options open up new paths of opportunity.

8. Virtual Asset Service Providers

With the growth of virtual assets has come the creation of virtual asset service providers (VASPs). VASPs are businesses that offer services to change between different virtual assets and exchange fiat currency for cryptocurrency, among other services.⁹⁴ Virtual assets can be transacted instantaneously and internationally, separate from financial institutions with AML or combatting the finance of terrorism (CFT) obligations.⁹⁵ Although significant VASPs like Coinbase and Binance have adhered to government regulations where they reside, approximately 75% of jurisdictions worldwide are only partially or not compliant with Financial Action Task Force (FATF) requirements are

⁹¹ “All Cryptocurrencies,” CoinMarketCap, accessed July 11, 2023, <https://coinmarketcap.com/all/views/all/>.

⁹² Dan Ashmore and Michael Adams, “Bitcoin Price History 2009 to 2022,” *Forbes Advisor*, April 16, 2024, <https://www.forbes.com/advisor/investing/cryptocurrency/bitcoin-price-history/>.

⁹³ Pavel Ramírez and Qayyah Moynihan, “13 Celebrities Who Back Cryptocurrency and May Own Millions in Bitcoin,” *Business Insider*, January 20, 2019, <https://www.businessinsider.com/13-celebrities-who-back-cryptocurrency-and-may-own-millions-in-bitcoin-2019-1>.

⁹⁴ Financial Action Task Force, *Targeted Update on Implementation of the FATF Standards on Virtual Assets and Virtual Asset Service Providers* (Paris: Financial Action Task Force, 2023), <https://www.fatf-gafi.org/en/publications/Fatfrecommendations/targeted-update-virtual-assets-vasps-2023.html>.

⁹⁵ Financial Action Task Force.

therefore very vulnerable to money laundering activity.⁹⁶ Regulation updates worldwide have been inadequate at preventing the use of VASPs to launder money.

Even though some VASPs are regulated and require know your customer (KYC) information from their customers, virtual assets and VASPs are still considered to offer varying degrees of anonymity because the only information on the blockchain are alphanumeric keys that do not contain any personal identification information.⁹⁷ Virtual assets and VASPs can offer mixers, multiple layers of encryption, stealth addresses to enhance anonymity.⁹⁸ Law enforcement should invest more resources into tracing crypto assets that transfer through VASPs, as they are a clear haven for money laundering.

A prime VASP money laundering example is that of Mark Alexander Hopkins, who lived in Texas and called himself “Doctor Bitcoin.” He exchanged between \$550,000 to \$1.5 million to Bitcoin for a TCO based in Nigeria that defrauded dozens of victims out of hundreds of thousands of dollars. Hopkins turned a blind eye to the TCO activity, failed to verify customers’ identifying information, and advised the TCO to keep deposits below \$9,500 to avoid reporting requirements. He was paid substantial fees for his exchange services.⁹⁹ The FBI arrested Hopkins after its investigation uncovered the digital money laundering activity. Hopkins plead guilty to illegally operating a VASP that exchanged U.S. dollars to virtual assets.

Another VASP money laundering case example is that of Bitcoin Mercantile Exchange (BitMEX). Arthur Hayes, Benjamin Delo, Samuel Reed, and Gregory Dwyer were the founders and executives of BitMEX, an offshore cryptocurrency derivatives exchange. They serviced U.S. citizens and were therefore obligated to the U.S. BSA laws, but they tried to avoid those requirements by registering the business in the Seychelles, a

⁹⁶ Financial Action Task Force.

⁹⁷ Schwarz et al., *Virtual Assets and Anti-Money Laundering*.

⁹⁸ Schwarz et al.

⁹⁹ “‘Doctor Bitcoin’ Pleads Guilty to Illegal Cash-to-Crypto Scheme,” U.S. Attorney’s Office, Northern District of Texas, June 29, 2021, <https://www.justice.gov/usao-ndtx/pr/doctor-bitcoin-pleads-guilty-illegal-cash-crypto-scheme>.

location seen as a money laundering haven.¹⁰⁰ One of the defendants bragged they could bribe a Seychelles regulator for much less than it would cost to bribe officials in the U.S. and other locations.¹⁰¹ As a result of the investigation, the FBI charged the owners of BitMEX for violating the Bank Secrecy Act by “failing to establish, implement, and maintain an anti-money laundering program.”¹⁰² FinCEN and the U.S. Commodity Futures Trading Commission issued a \$100 million civil money penalty against BitMEX.¹⁰³

9. Mapping Money Laundering Methods across Stages

The previous nine money laundering methods are not the only methods used by TCOs, but they are the most frequently used. The simpler methods of money laundering often only fit within one stage of the money laundering cycle. The more complex methods are flexible in their usability and can fit within one, two or all three stages. Table 1 provides a visual representation of the money laundering methods and how each fit with the stages of money laundering.

Table 1. Money Laundering Methods across Stages

Money Laundering Method	Placement	Layering	Integration
Structuring	X		
Shell Companies	X	X	
Funnel Accounts		X	

¹⁰⁰ “Founders and Executives of Off-Shore Cryptocurrency Derivatives Exchange Charged with Violation of the Bank Secrecy Act,” U.S. Attorney’s Office, Southern District of New York, October 1, 2020, <https://www.justice.gov/usao-sdny/pr/founders-and-executives-shore-cryptocurrency-derivatives-exchange-charged-violation>.

¹⁰¹ U.S. Attorney’s Office, Southern District of New York.

¹⁰² U.S. Attorney’s Office, Southern District of New York.

¹⁰³ Department of the Treasury, *National Money Laundering Risk Assessment*, 43.

Money Laundering Method	Placement	Layering	Integration
Foreign Currency Exchange		X	
Informal Value Transfer Systems	X	X	X
Trade Based Money Laundering	X	X	X
Peer to Peer Transfer Services		X	
Virtual/Crypto Assets	X	X	X
Virtual Asset Service Providers		X	

Law enforcement use multiple investigative techniques to track these money laundering methods, a task that will only become more challenging when criminals and money laundering networks begin to incorporate AI enabled tools.

B. U.S. EFFORTS TO COUNTER MONEY LAUNDERING

As criminal behavior evolves, so do the laws established to deter and stop such activity. Due to the nature of this cycle, legal authority reacts to the actions taken by criminals. In order to combat money laundering, it is imperative that the anti-money laundering community understand and adhere to all laws Congress enacts.

1. Legal Framework

Anti-money laundering laws are a recent phenomenon in relation to laws in the history of civilization. The first recorded laws were carved in stone during the reign of Babylonian King Hammurabi between 1792 and 1750 B.C.¹⁰⁴ Although what is now

¹⁰⁴ Marc Van De Mieroop, *King Hammurabi of Babylon: A Biography* (Hoboken, NJ: John Wiley & Sons, 2004), vii–x, ProQuest Ebook Central.

known as Hammurabi’s Code had 282 laws with 58 references to “money.”¹⁰⁵ none of the laws were to punish or counter the process of making illicit funds or proceeds appear legitimate, also known as money laundering. It took nearly 4,000 years before the first law to explicitly respond to money laundering came into existence.

Passed in 1970, the Bank Secrecy Act (BSA) was the first legislative action taken by the United States to counter the problem of money laundering.¹⁰⁶ The BSA required financial institutions to file reports of currency transactions and the import and export of monetary instruments. These reports also needed to be provided to federal agencies upon request. This legislation was a good first step to help law enforcement effectively disrupt criminal networks.

Several subsequent laws have been enacted to better enable law enforcement to dismantle TCOs by allowing law enforcement not only to identify when, where and who made large cash transactions, but also to identify and seize funds or assets derived from certain specified unlawful activity (SUA) and prosecute those involved with money laundering. Notable expansions of the anti-money laundering framework include the Money Laundering Control Act of 1986, the USA PATRIOT Act of 2001 and the Anti-Money Laundering Act of 2020. The Money Laundering Control Act of 1986 was focused on combatting the laundering of drug trafficking proceeds and established money laundering as a federal crime.¹⁰⁷ The Uniting and Strengthening America by Providing Appropriate Tools Required to Intercept and Obstruct Terrorism (USA PATRIOT) Act required financial institutions to establish anti-money laundering programs and verify the identity of their customers commonly referred to as Know Your Customer (KYC).¹⁰⁸ The ability of financial institutions to accurately conduct KYC checks was often difficult to determine because shell companies registered as being owned by other companies

¹⁰⁵ L. W. King, trans., “Code of Hammurabi,” The Avalon Project, accessed June 1, 2023, <https://avalon.law.yale.edu/ancient/hamframe.asp>.

¹⁰⁶ The Bank Secrecy Act.

¹⁰⁷ Money Laundering Control Act of 1986 and the Regulations Implementing the Bank Secrecy Act: Hearing before the Committee on Banking, Finance, and Urban Affairs, House of Representatives, 100th Cong. (1987), ProQuest.

¹⁰⁸ USA PATRIOT Act of 2001, Pub. L. 107–56, 115 Stat. 272, (2001).

concealed the true owners of these business accounts. The lack of ownership transparency was addressed by the establishment of beneficial ownership reporting requirement that was created by the Anti-Money Laundering Act of 2020 (AMLA).¹⁰⁹ In summary, these legislative developments have significantly enhanced law enforcement’s ability to combat TCOs and money laundering, ushering in a more robust framework for identifying, seizing and prosecuting illicit financial activities.

AMLA is the most recent law to address digitization in the twenty-first century. In July 2012, FinCEN required mandatory filings of CTRs and suspicious activity reports (SARs) to be filed electronically instead of on paper.¹¹⁰ FinCEN, an agency within the U.S. Treasury Department, receives CTRs, SARs and other anti-money laundering reports in its role to oversee policies to detect and prevent money laundering. It also shares intelligence with law enforcement.¹¹¹ By requiring electronically filed reports, it allowed for the opportunity for modern technology to assist with the analysis of the reports instead of relying on humans to spend endless hours reading and organizing the paper documents. Financial institutions used rules-based anti-money laundering software systems to identify suspicious activity based on threshold amounts or transactions involving countries known to have high-risk of money laundering.¹¹²

TCOs have created new methods to remain undetected by the rules-based anti-money laundering programs. To address AML circumvention measures by TCOs, Congress said the purposes of the AMLA was to improve coordination and information sharing, modernize anti-money laundering and counter terrorist financing laws, and “encourage technological innovation and adoption of new technology by financial

¹⁰⁹ William M. (Mac) Thornberry National Defense Authorization Act for Fiscal Year 2021, Pub. L 116–283, 134 Stat. 3388 (2021).

¹¹⁰ Steve Hudak, “FinCEN Marks the End of Paper SARs and CTRs” (Washington, DC: Financial Crimes Enforcement Network, June 29, 2012), <https://www.fincen.gov/news/news-releases/fincen-marks-end-paper-sars-and-ctrs>.

¹¹¹ “Frequently Asked Questions,” Financial Crimes Enforcement Network, accessed June 3, 2023, <https://www.fincen.gov/frequently-asked-questions>.

¹¹² “Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Its Role in Anti-Money Laundering,” Featurespace, May 27, 2022, <https://www.featurespace.com/newsroom/artificial-intelligence-ai-and-its-role-in-anti-money-laundering/>.

institutions to more effectively counter money laundering and the financing of terrorism.”¹¹³ Although Congress had passed other laws to expand on the BSA, AMLA was the first comprehensive reform that recognized the vast difference of technology and the ability to review large data in the twenty-first century. The BSA was established with the focus on individual reporting like the currency transaction reports and suspicious activity reports. Considering FinCEN’s electronic filing requirement and the sophisticated anti-money laundering compliance systems used by many financial institutions since then, AMLA addressed the digitization of financial data and updated the BSA.¹¹⁴

In conclusion, the passage of the AMLA marked a pivotal moment in the regulation of financial data in the twenty-first century, emphasizing the importance of the banking and financial sector to enhance AML efforts through adaptation of emerging technology.

2. Traditional AML Investigative Methods

There are several methods to build evidence in a money laundering investigation, but all criminal investigations follow three main stages of gathering evidence, analyzing the evidence, and then acting on the analytical product. Figure 2 shows how the investigative stages are connected in a cycle that can repeat as often as necessary to obtain enough evidence to show proof beyond a reasonable doubt that a person or persons committed criminal acts.

¹¹³ William M. (Mac) Thornberry National Defense Authorization Act for Fiscal Year 2021.

¹¹⁴ William M. (Mac) Thornberry National Defense Authorization Act for Fiscal Year 2021.

Figure 2. Stages of Criminal Investigations

This section will provide insights into the most common anti-money laundering investigative methods used by law enforcement. Due to the sensitivity of some of these methods, only a broad overview will be provided. If criminal organizations were to become aware of the details of police investigative methods, they would quickly adjust their modes of operation, exacerbating the challenges of criminal investigative efforts. The goals of financial investigations are to trace illicit proceeds for the purposes of prosecuting top management of TCOs in a criminal conspiracy and support seizures and forfeitures. The FBI, HSI, IRS-CI and USSS are the primary agencies investigating financial crimes and each of them use these investigative methods.

a. Intelligence from Sources of Information

A financial investigation can begin, or become enhanced, after information is provided directly to law enforcement. Information can be provided to law enforcement from different sources. Tip lines and websites allow a person to provide information directly to law enforcement either anonymously or with their contact information if they're

willing to have follow up discussions.¹¹⁵ Information can be divulged during interviews of defendants or people who are part of the money laundering process, sometimes unwittingly.¹¹⁶ Some sources of information already have pre-established working relationships with law enforcement. Some provide information because they have a sense of public duty or moral obligation. Others do it for financial gain if law enforcement is willing to pay for the information, and some give information against people who have wronged them or for law enforcement to focus on their competition if they are involved in criminal activity themselves. Law enforcement must weigh the reliability of the information being provided based on the source's motivation, history and trustworthiness.¹¹⁷ Some sources of information are documented as confidential informants to add further protection against retaliation from the TCO members being investigated. Sources can provide documents that show payments for drug shipments, value paid for the amount of drugs provided, who was involved and when the transactions occurred. Information provided by sources could also be where a suspect banks at, where and when they typically receive payments and how the payments are made. Law enforcement tries to obtain the most accurate information from the most reliable sources in order to build strong cases against money laundering organizations and TCOs.

(1) Review Trade Data

In the U.S., CBP and HSI have direct access to trade data. In order to identify trade-based money laundering, a money laundering method that moves the largest volume of illicit funds for TCOs, trade data must be analyzed.¹¹⁸ Review of the trade data can illuminate shell companies used to conceal the money laundering networks and TCOs. Law enforcement will look for indicators of trade-based money laundering, such as unusual shipping routes and mislabeling of commodities. Acquiring the skill to become proficient

¹¹⁵ Michael D. Lyman and Vicky Manning, *Practical Drug Enforcement*, 3rd ed. (New York: Routledge, 2006), 3.

¹¹⁶ Lyman and Manning, 92.

¹¹⁷ Lyman and Manning, 90–93.

¹¹⁸ Allan Swafford, “No Spin Cycle: Evaluating the Effectiveness of Homeland Security Investigations’ Efforts in Combating Money Laundering and Terrorist Financing” (master’s thesis, Naval Postgraduate School, 2023), 61, <https://hdl.handle.net/10945/72614>.

at finding numerous indicators of TBML can take years for some analysts and investigators. There are enormous volumes of trade occurring through the U.S. In 2022, the United States was the second-largest trading nation globally, with over \$7 trillion in trade of goods and services, maintaining commercial ties with over 200 countries, territories, and regional groups.¹¹⁹ If a TCO utilizes TBML as a method of laundering its proceeds, law enforcement must review the trade data in order to gather enough evidence needed to dismantle the money laundering infrastructure.

(2) Suspicious Travel

Reviewing a suspect's travel patterns can sometimes indicate activity consistent with bulk cash smuggling. Law enforcement can coordinate surveillance and interdiction operations of subjects after a few indicators are identified. Some of these indicators may include the method of payment, timing of flight purchases, and unnecessary connecting flights.¹²⁰ Interviews of suspects discovered to be traveling with large amounts of currency concealed in their bags are often fruitful. The suspects may corroborate information law enforcement had identified by other means. During an interview, a suspect may verify who gave them the money, where and to whom the funds were to be delivered and contact information of co-conspirators. Valuable information like this may not have been possible for law enforcement to obtain were it not for reviewing the suspect's travel patterns.

(3) Review BSA Data

The Bank Secrecy Act data that FinCEN maintains are CTRs, SARs, U.S. Treasury Form 8300s, currency and monetary instruments reports (CMIRs), Foreign Bank Account Records (FBARs). The Form 8300 is filed by any business that receives more than \$10,000 currency in a transaction.¹²¹ The CMIR is required to be filled out by persons who bring

¹¹⁹ "Countries & Regions," Office of the United States Trade Representative, accessed January 26, 2024, <https://ustr.gov/countries-regions>.

¹²⁰ Lyman and Manning, *Practical Drug Enforcement*, 182–83.

¹²¹ "Form 8300 and Reporting Cash Payments of Over \$10,000," IRS, accessed January 26, 2024, <https://www.irs.gov/businesses/small-businesses-self-employed/form-8300-and-reporting-cash-payments-of-over-10000>.

over \$10,000 currency or monetary instruments into or out of the U.S.¹²² According to the Money Laundering Control Act of 1986, it is mandated that “all persons subject to jurisdiction of the United States make an annual report of their interests in certain foreign bank accounts” in the FBAR form.¹²³ Law enforcement can review these BSA documents through FinCEN’s secure database, FinCEN Portal. Typically, a criminal investigator will request key word searches to find BSA data linked to their suspect’s name or bank account number, if known. If possible, matches populate, the investigator must open each document individually to confirm that the document indeed relates to the suspect of the investigation.

(4) Grand Jury Subpoenas

Once a suspect’s financial accounts have been identified, prosecutors will submit Grand Jury Subpoenas to request specific documents from financial institutions holding those accounts. A Grand Jury is a group of sixteen to twenty-three people who meet at court once or a few days a week for up to 24 months.¹²⁴ Grand Jury Subpoenas compel financial institutions to provide the requested documents within a set amount of time. If the volume of data is large, the financial institution will contact the requesting law enforcement officer or prosecutor to ask for an extension for delivery. The information provided pursuant to a Grand Jury Subpoena remains restricted to only the names of investigators and prosecutors working the investigation. If a new investigator is added to an investigation with Grand Jury material, the new investigator’s name must be added to the list before they will be able to view the financial documents obtained by a Grand Jury Subpoena. Because Grand Juries do not meet frequently, adding new names to the official list adds days or weeks to the analysis process. Once the investigation is complete or there is no longer a use for the information provided by the Grand Jury Subpoena, the

¹²² *Money Laundering Control Act of 1986 and the Regulations Implementing the Bank Secrecy Act: Hearing*

¹²³ *Money Laundering Control Act of 1986 and the Regulations Implementing the Bank Secrecy Act: Hearing*

¹²⁴ “Types of Juries,” United States Courts, accessed January 27, 2024, <https://www.uscourts.gov/services-forms/jury-service/types-juries>.

government will return the information to the Grand Jury.¹²⁵ Grand Jury Subpoenas are valuable tools that allow law enforcement to receive financial information from banks and other financial institutions that have been exploited by money laundering organizations.

(5) Financial Intelligence Units

Financial Intelligence Units are crucial in protecting against illegal money activities worldwide, working withing a complex system of international protocols and agreements to keep economies safe and combat TCOs. A Financial Intelligence Unit (FIU) is a government office that collects and studies financial information to protect the country's financial system from being used for illegal activities like money laundering and funding terrorism.¹²⁶ Law enforcement will seek information on foreign-based TCO or money laundering suspects from the FIU of the country where the suspects reside or conduct operations. However, not all countries will share their financial intelligence information. The United States is a member of the Egmont Group. The Egmont Group consists of 170 financial intelligence units that agree to share financial intelligence securely in furtherance of countering money laundering and financing of terrorism.¹²⁷ Requests for information through the Egmont Group are called Egmont Requests. Egmont requests can take a couple months or even a year to process, depending on the amount and format of data requested.

The information shared by FIUs through the Egmont Group cannot be used in criminal proceedings. However, information obtained from Egmont requests can help investigators positively identify unknown accounts, transactions, assets and associates. Once the previously unknown financial information is obtained from the Egmont Group response, investigators would need to make a formal request in the form of a Mutual Legal Assistance Treaty (MLAT) through the U.S. Department of Justice and the U.S. Department of State so the information could be introduced as evidence during judiciary

¹²⁵ "424. Procedure for Grand Jury Subpoena of Financial Records," Criminal Resource Manual, accessed January 27, 2024, <https://www.justice.gov/archives/jm/criminal-resource-manual-424-procedure-grand-jury-subpoena-financial-records>.

¹²⁶ "What We Do," Financial Crimes Enforcement Network (FinCEN), accessed January 26, 2024, <https://www.fincen.gov/what-we-do>.

¹²⁷ "About the Egmont Group," Egmont Group, accessed January 26, 2024, <https://egmontgroup.org/about/>.

proceedings.¹²⁸ An MLAT is also a time consuming process that can take months to process due to the bureaucracy of multiple government agencies as well as translations for non-English speaking countries. In summary, although obtaining financial information from foreign partners can be beneficial to criminal investigations, the process adds months to the investigative process.

b. Surveillance

Once a suspect or suspects have been identified, law enforcement will typically watch them in person. Goals of surveillance operations include understanding a pattern of life for an individual, identifying co-conspirators, witnessing illicit activity, identifying methods and means of how proceeds are transferred or stored.¹²⁹ Law enforcement will take notes, photos and videos of surveillances, which can be used later as evidence for obtaining search, arrest and seizure warrants, as well as for court proceedings. Surveillances are conducted for hours at a time during multiple days spread over a few weeks before ample evidence is gathered. Sometimes law enforcement does not gain much beneficial information from conducting surveillance because the suspect is savvy of law enforcement presence or conducts all illicit activity online. For this reason, surveillance is only one of many methods used to investigate financial crimes.

c. Undercover Methods

Another way to identify layers of a TCO network is to launder the illicit proceeds for the TCO in an undercover capacity. Undercover officers approach a member of a TCO and claim to have the ability to move illicit proceeds for a fee.¹³⁰ Once the fee is agreed upon, the TCO will deliver funds to the undercover officers. The TCO will then provide instructions for where/whom to send the funds. Law enforcement can either release the funds as instructed and continue to follow the money or seize the funds. Direct dialogue

¹²⁸ “2012 International Narcotics Control Strategy Report (INCSR),” March 7, 2012, Bureau of International Narcotics and Law Enforcement Affairs, accessed January 26, 2024, <https://2009-2017.state.gov/j/inl/rls/nrcrpt/2012/vol2/184110.htm>.

¹²⁹ Lyman and Manning, *Practical Drug Enforcement*.

¹³⁰ R. E. Bell, “Undercover Sting Operations in Money-Laundering Cases,” *Journal of Money Laundering Control* 4, no. 4 (2001): 333–43, <https://doi.org/10.1108/eb027283>.

with TCO members can help law enforcement prove knowledge and intent of money laundering.

d. Analyze Financial Information

Once criminal investigators have TCO financial documents, they must analyze all documents thoroughly. Financial documents may include bank statements, wire transfers, check deposits and withdrawals, cash deposits slips, cash withdrawal logs, P2P transfers, transfers to crypto asset exchangers, electronic communications with account or other financial information, hand-written ledgers, or encrypted data stored on a foreign server. There are two fundamental goals of financial analysis in a money laundering investigation. The first is to prove the elements of money laundering so criminals can be charged and prosecuted.¹³¹ Criminal investigators must uncover any complex financial schemes used by the suspects. For example, if a business account is opened with the account application stating it would conduct local business in U.S. dollars, but the account activity shows incoming wire transfers from numerous foreign banks in different parts of the world, that activity would not be what is expected for the type of business it claims to be. Being able to explain abnormal activity with aid investigators in articulating why there is probable cause or proof beyond a reasonable doubt that the suspect engaged in money laundering.

The second fundamental goal of financial analysis is to identify, seize and forfeit illicit proceeds and assets of TCOs to disrupt and dismantle those organizations. Investigators must trace the flow of illicit proceeds to show where the funds came from, where the funds went and what other people or entities were involved.¹³² Conducting full financial tracing helps investigators identify assets purchased with or used in furtherance of specified unlawful activity. Sometimes evidence of financial crime is scarce, even after diligent efforts of surveillance, search warrants, subpoenas and other investigative methods. In those instances, investigators should analyze a suspect's income, assets, and

¹³¹ Financial Action Task Force, *Operational Issues Financial Investigations Guidance* (Paris: Financial Action Task Force, 2012), <https://www.fatf-gafi.org/en/publications/Methodsandtrends/Operationalissues-financialinvestigationguidance.html>.

¹³² Financial Action Task Force.

expenditures over time to identify unexplained wealth.¹³³ Assets can be seized civilly once investigators demonstrate a thorough unexplained income analysis. The seizure and forfeiture of TCO assets greatly hinders TCOs from being able to continue their illegal enterprise.

Many law enforcement agencies are still adapting to TCO use of crypto assets. Since the creation of Bitcoin in 2009, TCOs have been using crypto assets to move, conceal and launder illicit proceeds. Investigators can find crypto asset transactions because they are publicly available on blockchains. However, not enough law enforcement officers and analysts are keeping pace with TCOs with regards to crypto assets. Some investigators avoid working the financial aspect cases involving crypto assets because they are unfamiliar with how they function and may not want to learn something new. Today's law enforcement needs to remove the stigma that crypto investigations are harder to investigate because people don't understand crypto assets. Comprehensive blockchain analysis training for novice and seasoned financial investigators needs to be provided to more criminal investigators because money laundering through crypto assets has greatly increased in recent years. According to a report by Chainalysis in early 2024, the average value of crypto assets received by illicit addresses from 2021 through 2023 was approximately \$29 billion, compared to less than \$9 billion average for the three previous years.¹³⁴

In the fight against digital financial crimes, authorities have turned to cutting-edge technologies for solutions. Investigators within the Department of Justice and Department of Homeland Security, including the FBI and HSI, utilize blockchain analytics software to exploit the enduring nature of transaction records on public blockchains. Through these analytical tools, investigators can link specific digital currency wallets with payments emanating from illicit activity. Investigators, using machine-learning algorithms employed by these tools, are also able to scrutinize behavioral trends and decode data from the

¹³³ Financial Action Task Force, 28.

¹³⁴ "2024 Crypto Crime Trends: Illicit Activity Down as Scamming and Stolen Funds Fall, But Ransomware and Darknet Markets See Growth," Chainalysis, January 18, 2024, <https://www.chainalysis.com/blog/2024-crypto-crime-report-introduction/>.

blockchain.¹³⁵ Application of blockchain analytics by DOJ and DHS signifies a pivotal advancement in law enforcement’s capacity to combat cybercrime, representing a crucial step in adapting investigative techniques to the evolving landscape of crypto asset transactions.

e. Search Warrants

A key method of acquiring evidence in any criminal investigation is through search warrants. In the U.S., a law enforcement officer will write an affidavit describing evidence of criminal activity to show probable cause that more evidence of the crime will be found at or within a location to be searched. The affidavit will be reviewed by a judge who will then approve or deny the search warrant, in adherence to the Fourth Amendment, which prohibits unreasonable search and seizure.¹³⁶ In financial investigations, search warrants may be conducted at residences, places of business, financial institutions, safety deposit boxes, electronic devices, emails and other online platforms. Some of the best evidence in financial investigations comes through search warrants because law enforcement encounters financial documents, communications and other physical evidence directly.

3. Stages of Investigations

Criminal investigations can be sorted into three distinct stages: information gathering, analysis of the information, and actions based on the analysis. Most investigations do not move through these stages in a linear fashion. The investigative stages are fluid and iterative. Sometimes new information comes while analysis is ongoing. Post analytical actions include executing search, seizure and arrest warrants in furtherance of prosecution. Investigators may also decide they need more information after analyzing all evidence gathered to that point. Analysis of financial data often identifies accounts, entities or other sources of information that needs to be reviewed and analyzed. Table 2 illustrates

¹³⁵ U. S. Government Accountability Office, “As Virtual Currency Use in Human and Drug Trafficking Increases, So Do the Challenges for Federal Law Enforcement,” *WatchBlog: Following the Federal Dollar* (blog), February 24, 2022, <https://www.gao.gov/blog/virtual-currency-use-human-and-drug-trafficking-increases-so-do-challenges-federal-law-enforcement>.

¹³⁶ U.S. Const. amend. IV (annotated), <https://constitution.congress.gov/browse/amendment-4/>.

how traditional investigative methods are applied throughout the stages of an investigation process.

Table 2. Traditional Investigative Techniques: A Stage-by-Stage Overview

Investigative Method	Gather Information	Analyze	Act
Source Intelligence	X		
Surveillance	X		
Suspicious Travel		X	
Undercover Operation	X		
Review Trade Data		X	
Review BSA Data	X	X	
Grand Jury Subpoenas	X		
Financial Intel Unit Information	X		
Financial Analysis		X	
Blockchain Analysis		X	
Arrest Warrants			X
Search Warrants	X		
Seizure Warrants			X

Analysis of Table 2 reveals a categorization of investigative techniques that correspond with practical aspects of conducting investigations. It highlights the need for adjusting investigative approaches as cases evolve through phases, ranging from initial fact-gathering to the intricate processes of analyzing evidence and decisive legal action. Many of these methods, sometimes all, will be used during investigations of typical and complex money laundering organizations. Each of the warrants require analysis of previously obtained information to demonstrate probable cause, enabling a judge to authorize the legal action. While seizure and arrest warrants can be final actions prior to

legal proceedings, they can also yield valuable information on new money trails and upper-level members of the money laundering or criminal organizations.

Due to the continuous feedback from information gathering, analysis and subsequent actions that bring more information, document driven investigations of financial crimes require numerous iterations. Each iteration brings more data that needs to be analyzed. The analysis stage of money laundering investigations takes the greatest amount of time and human resources. Some investigators are deterred from pursuing financial investigations because of the extended amount of time necessary to complete them. Lack of qualified financial investigators is a pain point to law enforcement's efforts to dismantle TCOs and money laundering organizations. New analytical tools with generative AI can greatly reduce the analysis timeframe. Adoption of such tools will speed up the investigative process and encourage more investigators to employ financial investigative techniques, resulting in more criminals being arrested and prosecuted more frequently as greater amounts of their illicit proceeds are seized and forfeited. Although financial investigations require significant analysis of greater volumes of data than other investigations, law enforcement use of AI can relieve that pain point.

C. NEW ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE CAPABILITIES

In the last decade, artificial intelligence technology has enhanced capabilities and expanded applicable uses. Today, AI is being used by a myriad of occupational fields, including medical (cancer detection and treatment), agricultural (determine crop growth based on geospatial analysis of soil quality), financial (detect fraud), engineering (detect damage caused by natural disasters), and energy sectors (generate safe and efficient energy in a power plant).¹³⁷ These occupations involve tasks that have been successfully automated by AI. The continual integration of AI across diverse sectors will not only reshape the labor market but also indicates a profound shift in societal functions and the future of global innovation.

¹³⁷ Michael Webb, "The Impact of Artificial Intelligence on the Labor Market," SSRN Scholarly Paper (Stanford University, January 2020), <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3482150>.

AI involves a variety of technologies, each with its own complexities and uses. Machine Learning is an important subset of AI where algorithms make decisions informed by past data or experiences.¹³⁸ Within machine learning, Neural Networks process information through a web of nodes that, much like synapses in the brain, pass signals through multiple layers to reach a decision.¹³⁹ Deep learning, a further specialization, employs these networks to interpret raw input through successive layers, each providing a more abstract view of the data.¹⁴⁰ Natural Language Processing leverages these models to analyze and comprehend human language, predicting the likelihood of various expressions.¹⁴¹ Open AI's ChatGPT is the most prominent natural language processing model today. AI technology continues to develop and become more complex.

In the realm of machine learning, there are two primary learning models. Supervised Learning uses algorithms that are training on labeled data to produce expected outcomes.¹⁴² Unsupervised Learning relies on patterns in unlabeled data to reveal unforeseen results.¹⁴³ A sophisticated branch of deep learning is Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs), consisting of dual networks called the generator and the discriminator, which are put into a competition to produce increasingly authentic outputs, indistinguishable from real data.¹⁴⁴ An application of GANs is the creation of Deepfakes, where audio or visual content is convincingly altered, often for misinformation.¹⁴⁵ The strategic development and application of these machine learning models, particularly the ability of GANs to create undetectable Deepfakes, highlight the importance to implement robust authentication methods and raises profound ethical questions in the development of AI.

¹³⁸ Beccia, Habre, and Lerner, "Integrating AI, Machine Learning."

¹³⁹ Nilsson, *The Quest for Artificial Intelligence*, 64–67.

¹⁴⁰ LeCun, Bengio, and Hinton, "Deep Learning," 436.

¹⁴¹ Russell, Norvig, and Davis, *Artificial Intelligence*, 860.

¹⁴² Beccia, Habre, and Lerner, "Integrating AI, Machine Learning."

¹⁴³ Beccia, Habre, and Lerner.

¹⁴⁴ Pereira, "A Machine Learning Approach."

¹⁴⁵ Broinowski, "Deepfake Nightmares," 110.

D. CONCLUSION

Terrorist and criminal organizations fervently innovate how they launder illicit funds with more complexity to avoid law enforcement detection. Although anti-money laundering legislation is relatively new in modern history, laws are continually updated with more frequency, especially as lawmakers recognize the need to keep pace with emerging technologies. Law enforcement has extensive experience at developing methods to identify, investigate and prosecute these transnational criminal and terrorist organizations with a focus of targeting their financial support structures to severely disrupt or dismantle those organizations. As artificial intelligence becomes more advanced and user friendly, both criminals and law enforcement will need to utilize AI tools to pursue their conflicting goals with more successes.

III. AI VS. AI: COMBATTING CRIMINAL USE OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE

This chapter describes how AI can be used by criminal organizations to launder money. Next, it describes different AI tools used to investigate financial crimes by the financial sector and law enforcement. Financial institutions initially developed these tools to remain compliant of AML regulations and combat fraud. When conducting financial investigations, law enforcement will often benefit from anti-money laundering practices done by financial institutions. Finally, the chapter discusses some of the ways law enforcement is currently incorporating AI into its investigative toolset. This chapter demonstrates that criminals are using AI to advance money laundering while law enforcement recognize the threat but lag behind in development of effective AI anti-money laundering tools.

A. CRIMINAL USE OF AI

Whereas some scholars assert that AI will bring peril to humankind, others maintain that it will revolutionize every sector of society. In 2018, scholars began publishing solutions to prevent and combat malicious AI, though academic debate on this topic is limited. This thesis focuses on how law enforcement can use AI to enhance money laundering investigations and considering criminal application of financial crimes enhanced by AI is imperative.

Between 2017 and 2023, several scholars have predicted “the malicious use of AI.” Kevin Peters asserts “that emerging AI technologies will likely offer new access points to target potential victims and will add a new level of sophistication to cybercrime.”¹⁴⁶ Peters explains that TCOs and other criminals who use the internet to promote and hide their illegal activity engage on Dark Net marketplaces and share information on how to avoid detection by law enforcement. He conjects that AI algorithms could be sold through the

¹⁴⁶ Kevin M. Peters, “21st Century Crime: How Malicious Artificial Intelligence Will Impact Homeland Security” (master’s thesis, Naval Postgraduate School, 2019), 76, <https://www.hsdl.org/c/abstract/?docid=825201>.

Dark Net in furtherance of illicit activity. AI advancements could be used in autonomous weapon systems, deepfakes, identity theft and virtual kidnapping, according to Peters.

Building on this idea, Seth Jones and Patrick Johnston aptly warn that malicious actors will exploit readily available technologies to safeguard their online operations.¹⁴⁷ According to Jones and Johnston, motivated by increasingly advanced, user-friendly software technology and accessible online resources, malicious actors are more inclined to adopt emerging technologies, fostering more significant innovation independently.¹⁴⁸ Jones and Johnston assert malicious actors will use encryption, location-masking tools and anonymizers to conceal their online activity. Taís Blauth, Oskar Gstrein and Andrej Zwitter bring up an entirely new concern by differentiating unintended outcomes of AI use and its intended malicious use.¹⁴⁹ Blauth et al. point out that AI neural networks can inadvertently divulge sensitive information that was used in its training. For example, when using a software with an AI large language model and typing a text phrase like “my ID number is,” the model could auto populate an actual ID number of a different person.¹⁵⁰ Blauth et al. also discuss the unintended consequence of AI tools that speed up financial analysis and decision making can be used to manipulate the stock market. They say that developers must comprehensively identify vulnerabilities within AI systems and address them to mitigate risks and opportunities for malicious actors. In sum, according to the literature, the evolution of AI advancements continues to introduce new vulnerabilities requiring persistent oversight.

Deepfakes are an example of open-source AI applications that anybody can use for fun or malicious intent. Konstantin Panserev observes that developers created apps used

¹⁴⁷ Seth G. Jones and Patrick B. Johnston, “The Future of Insurgency,” *Studies in Conflict & Terrorism* 36, no. 1 (2013): 1, <https://doi.org/10.1080/1057610X.2013.739077>.

¹⁴⁸ Jones and Johnston, 17.

¹⁴⁹ Taís Fernanda Blauth, Oskar Josef Gstrein, and Andrej Zwitter, “Artificial Intelligence Crime: An Overview of Malicious Use and Abuse of AI,” *IEEE Access* 10 (2022): 3–4, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2022.3191790>.

¹⁵⁰ Blauth, Gstrein, and Zwitter, 4.

to create deepfakes for entertainment purposes, not nefarious intent.¹⁵¹ He purports that the application Fake TV News Maker provides “fun” by allowing anyone to create news that appears to come from well-known news sources. In a frequently-cited publication focused on exposing deepfakes, scholars Santosh Kolagati, Thenuga Priyadharshini, and V. Mary Anita Rajam concede that deepfakes can have beneficial effects—creating voices to assist blind people, for example—they insist that negative implications of deepfakes outweigh their positive applications.¹⁵² National security threats are among the most concerning possibilities of deepfakes. Anna Broinowski emphasizes this point when she describes the 2022 hacked broadcast of Ukraine President Volodymyr Zelensky purportedly calling for Ukraine soldiers to surrender.¹⁵³ According to Broinowski, although news media quickly dispelled it as fake, more deepfakes of this potential magnitude will continue to occur, but with improved quality that will make discrediting them more difficult.¹⁵⁴ Thus, we must be cognizant of the balance between innovation and responsibility, and address the urgent need to improve ways to identify and counteract malicious deepfakes.

Countering malicious AI sparks a range of responses. Although Blauth and her colleagues do a good job describing potential problems AI poses to society, they do not provide any recommendations to mitigate those problems.¹⁵⁵ In contrast, Peters recommends developing national strategies to combat malicious AI, increasing government engagement with private industry, and expanding international partnerships to combat AI-enabled cybercrime.¹⁵⁶ Similarly, in her examination of economic security,

¹⁵¹ Konstantin A. Pantserev, “The Malicious Use of AI-Based Deepfake Technology as the New Threat to Psychological Security and Political Stability,” in *Cyber Defence in the Age of AI, Smart Societies and Augmented Humanity*, ed. Hamid Jahankhani et al. (Cham, Switzerland: Springer International Publishing, 2020), 38, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-35746-7_3.

¹⁵² Santosh Kolagati, Thenuga Priyadharshini, and V. Mary Anita Rajam, “Exposing Deepfakes Using a Deep Multilayer Perceptron – Convolutional Neural Network Model,” *International Journal of Information Management Data Insights* 2, no. 1 (April 2022): 1–2, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jjimei.2021.100054>.

¹⁵³ Broinowski, “Deepfake Nightmares,” 119.

¹⁵⁴ Broinowski, 120.

¹⁵⁵ Blauth, Gstrein, and Zwitter, “Artificial Intelligence Crime.”

¹⁵⁶ Peters, “21st Century Crime,” 78–81.

Laura Tyson recommends that the United States create international cooperation agreements to protect against dual-use technologies, including AI.¹⁵⁷ Tyson proposes science and technology become a priority in international agreements made with allies to exchange and protect new scientific and engineering information as a way to decrease the likelihood of adversaries obtaining technologies vital to national security. Due to the global impact of malicious AI, international cooperation will be essential. The more difficult task is formulating the best methods to share information while taking actions that do not duplicate efforts or counteract each other.

B. AI TOOLS USED TO INVESTIGATE FINANCIAL CRIMES

Although financial institutions identify anomalous behavior, they cannot prosecute so they work closely with law enforcement to initiate or support investigations. The legal framework developed to thwart money laundering is driving businesses in the finance industry to create or use emerging technology to identify and report risk, fraud, and suspicious activity. Therefore, AI is increasingly used in AML tools. As a result, suspicious activity is identified quickly, and law enforcement is able to review recent activity while following the illicit proceeds of suspected criminals. Law enforcement is increasing its use of AI while considering private security and safety implications. This section will provide key examples of these tools used to investigate financial crimes.

1. Banking and Beyond: AI Tools Used by the Financial Sector

When the U.S. Congress passed the Anti-Money Laundering Act (AMLA) of 2020, it said the AMLA intended “to encourage technological innovation and adoption of new technology by financial institutions to more effectively counter money laundering and the financing of terrorism.”¹⁵⁸ Financial institutions have embraced the push toward modernization and are pioneering enhancement of their AML programs with the help of AI.

¹⁵⁷ Laura D. Tyson and Bruce Guile, “Innovation-Based Economic Security,” *Issues in Science and Technology* 37, no. 4 (Summer 2021): 47, ProQuest.

¹⁵⁸ William M. (Mac) Thornberry National Defense Authorization Act for Fiscal Year 2021.

Today, one would be hard pressed to find volumes of paper documents previously hoarded by banking institutions. The digitization of financial records yielded enormous amounts of data that were effectively analyzed with the help of technological innovations like “big data” and artificial intelligence. Many financial institutions have large data siloed among different data sources. To analyze the different data sets, financial institutions are creating big data architectures to centralize the information.¹⁵⁹ Artificial Intelligence, specifically machine learning, has assisted financial institutions with the analysis of big data.

Traditionally, financial institutions use rule-based and scenario-based artificial intelligence, gleaned from red flag indicators and subject matter expert judgment, to monitor transactions.¹⁶⁰ This type of AML tool is reactionary and maintains the pattern of being constantly trying to catch up to the TCOs. Of all the various types of artificial intelligence, financial institutions have been increasing their use of machine learning and natural language processing with their risk management, fraud and anti-money laundering programs. Their uses have been developing over the past two decades and have seen significant increases of use and functionality in the last five years.¹⁶¹ The increasing adoption of AI tools by financial institutions for their AML programs is crucial because it allows for more proactive detection and prevention of illicit activities.

a. Risk and Fraud Detection

Financial institutions first used machine learning methods to assess credit risks since the early 2000s. Early pioneers that put artificial intelligence to assess risk found that when generalized classifications of large datasets were combined with traditional credit

¹⁵⁹ John Soldatos and Dimosthenis Kyriazis, eds., *Big Data and Artificial Intelligence in Digital Finance: Increasing Personalization and Trust in Digital Finance Using Big Data and AI* (Cham, Switzerland: Springer Nature, 2022), 4, <https://link.springer.com/book/10.1007/978-3-030-94590-9>.

¹⁶⁰ P. K. Doppalapudi, “Machine Learning: A Game-Changer in the Fight against Money Laundering,” ACAMS Today, January 19, 2023, <https://www.acamstoday.org/machine-learning-a-game-changer-in-the-fight-against-money-laundering/>.

¹⁶¹ Soldatos and Kyriazis, *Big Data and Artificial Intelligence in Digital Finance*.

factors, the predictive power of the model was greatly increased.¹⁶² Studies done by Vlademir Olej, Petr Hajek, A. Lahsasna, R.N. Aninon and The Ying Wah demonstrate that the use of machine learning to predict creditworthiness was experimental during the early stage prior to 2010.¹⁶³ Although results of the Olej et. al. study showed supervised learning yielded better results than semi-supervised or unsupervised learning, Lahsasna et. al. argue their study demonstrates the ability of semi-supervised learning methods can bring accurate results with more transparency. Machine learning in the use of detecting credit card fraud has also been used by financial institutions in the early twenty-first century. A study published in 2018 tested and compared three machine learning techniques to detect credit card fraud and trained their model to predict whether a credit card is fraudulent or not with accuracy of 99.75%.¹⁶⁴ The convergence of machine learning innovations and financial analysis not only enhances the accuracy of credit and fraud detection models but also paves the way for more sophisticated and transparent financial risk assessment methods in the future.

b. Monitoring for Money Laundering

Natural language processing has also contributed to anti-money laundering programs. In natural language processing, computers use language models to “predict the probability distribution of language expressions,” according to Stuart Russell, Peter Novig and Ernest Davis.¹⁶⁵ These language models use a large amount of vocabulary within a

¹⁶² Bart van Liebergen, “Machine Learning: A Revolution in Risk Management and Compliance?,” *The Capco Institute Journal of Financial Transformation*, no. 45 (2017): 60–67, <https://www.capco.com/Capco-Institute/Journal-45-Transformation/Machine-learning-a-revolution-in-risk-management-and-compliance>.

¹⁶³ Petr Hajek and Vladimír Olej, “Municipal Creditworthiness Modelling by Kernel-Based Approaches with Supervised and Semi-Supervised Learning,” in *Engineering Applications of Neural Networks*, ed. Dominic Palmer-Brown et al., Communications in Computer and Information Science (Berlin: Springer, 2009), 35–43, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-03969-0_4; and A. Lahsasna, R.N. Ainon, and Teh Ying Wah, “Intelligent Credit Scoring Model Using Soft Computing Approach,” in *2008 International Conference on Computer and Communication Engineering*, 2008, 396–402, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICCCE.2008.4580635>.

¹⁶⁴ Tanupriya Choudhury et al., “An Efficient Way to Detect Credit Card Fraud Using Machine Learning Methodologies,” in *2018 Second International Conference on Green Computing and Internet of Things (ICGCIoT)*, 2018, 591–97, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICGCIoT.2018.8753077>.

¹⁶⁵ Russell, Norvig, and Davis, *Artificial Intelligence*, 860.

database which uses algorithmic models that require millions or billions of written text examples to have good training results. Chen, Li and Wang claim that because the amount of vocabulary needed to adequately train natural language processing models is so vast, pre-training technology has been commonly used since 2018.¹⁶⁶ After training has been done, the natural language processing can be applied to detect fraudulent emails and inaccurate translations that are common in transnational fraud communications, according to Chen et. al. Natural language processing can also facilitate checks on watch lists and sanctions in almost real time as international transactions occur.¹⁶⁷ Therefore, the integration of natural language processing into anti-money laundering efforts represents a significant leap forward in automating and enhancing the detection of fraudulent activities.

c. Currency Authentication

The use of artificial intelligence in the prevention of financial fraud has gone beyond just financial institutions. At the 2018 Canadian Conference on Artificial Intelligence, Tamarafinide Dittimi and Ching Suen presented their findings on the research and development of a mobile phone application capable of recognizing banknotes. They concluded that the system would work on any currency in the world.¹⁶⁸ It is not a way to identify counterfeit notes, however. The U.S. Currency Education Program advertises a “Cash Assist” mobile app as being the “perfect training companion for cash handlers across industries who need guidance on how to authenticate Federal Reserve notes.”¹⁶⁹ The app provides information about security features of specific bank notes but does not alert the user to counterfeit items. That decision is left to the human physically inspecting the

¹⁶⁶ Wei-Yu Chen, Shing-Han Li, and Yung-Hsin Wang, “Research on Natural Language Processing in Financial Risk Detection,” in *Cognitive Cities*, ed. Jian Shen et al., Communications in Computer and Information Science (Singapore: Springer, 2020), 448–55, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-15-6113-9_50.

¹⁶⁷ Alejandro Martinez, “Getting Value from NLP for Fraud Detection,” *Forbes*, May 10, 2023, <https://www.forbes.com/sites/forbesbusinesscouncil/2023/05/10/getting-value-from-nlp-for-fraud-detection/>.

¹⁶⁸ Tamarafinide V. Dittimi and Ching Y. Suen, “Mobile App for Detection of Counterfeit Banknotes,” in *Advances in Artificial Intelligence*, ed. Ebrahim Bagheri and Jackie C.K. Cheung, Lecture Notes in Computer Science (Cham, Switzerland: Springer International Publishing, 2018), 156–68, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-89656-4_13.

¹⁶⁹ “Cash Assist Mobile App,” U.S. Currency Education Program, accessed June 4, 2023, <https://www.uscurrency.gov/educational-materials/cash-assist-app>.

banknote.¹⁷⁰ The expansion of artificial intelligence into diverse applications highlights its potential to revolutionize not only fraud detection in the financial sector, but also to enhance the global accessibility and understanding of currency authentication practices of merchants and vendors.

2. Law Enforcement Use of AI

Law enforcement has been using AI in various forms to aid in criminal investigations. This section of the chapter highlights a few of those AI uses by federal agencies, namely HSI and the FBI. The final examples provided are specific to financial crime investigations.

a. Homeland Security Investigations' Use of AI

Homeland Security Investigations (HSI) has been improving its analytical tools that use AI since 2019 when it created the HSI Innovation Lab.¹⁷¹ The purpose for the HSI Innovation Lab is to allow for input from special agents and criminal analysts to direct how technological solutions should be developed based on the gaps identified during current investigations. The analytical platform developed by the HSI Innovation Lab is called the Repository for Analytics in a Virtualized Environment (RAVEN).¹⁷² RAVEN is a cloud-based platform that provides data analytics, risk scoring and reporting to support HSI's mission to detect, deter, and mitigate threats to national security and public safety.

(1) Communication Analysis

RAVEN uses AI and machine learning for data tagging and classification to assist HSI with tools that streamline review of large data evidence. The Email Analytics Tool can translate foreign languages to English, organizes documents by categories and enables

¹⁷⁰ U.S. Currency Education Program.

¹⁷¹ "HSI Innovation Lab," U.S. Immigration and Customs Enforcement, accessed July 12, 2023, <https://www.ice.gov/partnerships-centers/innovation-lab>.

¹⁷² "AI Use Case Inventory," U.S. Department of Homeland Security, accessed July 12, 2023, https://www.dhs.gov/data/AI_inventory.

special agents to identify how TCOs are structured.¹⁷³ The Mobile Device Analytics tool improves the efficiency to identify key information required to show elements of the crime and make connections among TCO members based on information pulled from cell phones.¹⁷⁴

Both tools use natural language processing on the narrative portions of raw datasets ingested by RAVEn.¹⁷⁵ Prior to the development of the RAVEn Email Analytics Tool, my coworkers and I would spend days reading through emails received from search warrants by using key-word searches. The machine learning employed by RAVEn will greatly reduce time needed to review and analyze such data. The natural language processing integrated to the new email tool allows the system to extract meaning not only from single words, but also from entire sentences.¹⁷⁶ The natural language processing identifies individuals, businesses, vehicles, phone numbers and addresses, and finds interconnections and patterns among those entities, which is done by analyzing multiple reports across different datasets.¹⁷⁷ For example, an investigator may notice that the main subject of the investigation has frequent email communication with a single email address, email X. The investigator can then prompt email analytics tool to identify any and all connections among the information contained in the email search warrant as well as other law enforcement databases to identify who is associated with email X and that it is linked to phone B, which also has significant communication with other conspirators of the TCO.

(2) Language Translation

HSI's RAVEn also implemented a language translator tool provided by Systran. Systran offers adaptive AI-assisted translation services of over 100 languages to government, healthcare, financial and education industries by using deep learning neural

¹⁷³ U.S. Department of Homeland Security.

¹⁷⁴ U.S. Department of Homeland Security.

¹⁷⁵ Alysa D. Erichs, *Privacy Impact Assessment for the Repository for Analytics in a Virtualized Environment (RAVEn)*, DHS/ICE/PIA-055 (Washington, DC: U.S. Department of Homeland Security, 2020), 30, <https://www.dhs.gov/sites/default/files/publications/privacy-pia-ice055-raven-may2020.pdf>.

¹⁷⁶ Erichs, 30.

¹⁷⁷ Erichs, 30.

networks.¹⁷⁸ The machine learning used by Systran increases the efficiency, accuracy and quality of translating plain text, word documents and portable document formats (PDFs).¹⁷⁹ This innovative tool saves the government both time and money. Instead of sending documents written in Arabic to a contracted translation service, waiting weeks for the pages to be translated to English and paying hefty fees, investigators can have the English translation within minutes.

(3) TBML Analysis

The HSI Trade Transparency Unit (TTU) detects and investigates TBML by analyzing financial information and trade data, including data shared between the United States and partner countries. Special agents and analysts use the Data Analysis and Research for Trade Transparency System (DARTTS) to pinpoint anomalies and suspicious activity that indicate TCO money laundering or other crimes.¹⁸⁰ HSI is in the process of improving an older version of a similar system that resided on a vendor-owned operating platform named FALCON. The new version will be housed on the HSI RAVEN platform.¹⁸¹

Case Example

Using the DARTTS database, HSI Miami special agents identified suspicious trade of gold from South America to the United States. From 2012 to 2016, Samer H. Barrage, Renato J. Rodriguez, and Juan P. Granda conspired to purchase billions of dollars' worth of criminally derived gold through Elemental LLC, a precious metals company.¹⁸² The investigation found that Barrage and his co-conspirators believed or knew the gold was

¹⁷⁸ "AI Powered Neural Machine Translation," Systran, accessed July 13, 2023, <https://www.systran.us/en-us/>.

¹⁷⁹ U.S. Department of Homeland Security, "AI Use Case Inventory."

¹⁸⁰ U.S. Department of Homeland Security, *Privacy Impact Assessment for the Data Analysis & Research for Trade Transparency System*, DHS/ICE/PIA-038 (Washington, DC: U.S. Department of Homeland Security, 2023), <https://www.dhs.gov/publication/dhsicepia-038-data-analysis-research-trade-transparency-system-dartts>.

¹⁸¹ U.S. Department of Homeland Security.

¹⁸² "Four Peruvian Members of Multi-Billion Dollar, International Gold Money Laundering Scheme Indicted," U.S. Attorney's Office, Southern District of Florida, January 9, 2018, <https://www.justice.gov/usao-sdfl/pr/four-peruvian-members-multi-billion-dollar-international-gold-money-laundering-scheme>.

derived from narcotics trafficking, illegal mining, and other crimes. Barrage, Rodriguez and Granda admitted guilt for laundering illicit proceeds. Elemental neglected to verify the legitimacy of gold sources and the identities of suppliers, frequently accepting gold linked to criminal networks. On March 16, 2018, the company pleaded guilty to violating the BSA by failing to maintain a proper AML program. Subsequently, Elemental had to forfeit \$15 million.¹⁸³

b. The FBI's Use of AI

The Federal Bureau of Investigations (FBI) employs artificial intelligence in some of its investigative tools, including facial recognition and DNA analysis. Both of these tools effectively aid law enforcement in identifying suspected criminals or terrorists.

(1) Facial Recognition

The FBI uses AI and machine learning in its facial recognition tools. These tools are utilized in the FBI's Next Generation Identification (NGI) System and the Facial Analysis, Comparison, and Evaluation (FACE) Services Unit.¹⁸⁴ The NGI System maintains booking photographs linked to fingerprints and criminal history records. It also provides "automated [facial recognition] searches by authorized local, state, tribal, and federal law enforcement agencies."¹⁸⁵ For 18 months beginning October 2017, law enforcement users of the NGI System submitted over 150,000 facial recognition requests to the FBI.¹⁸⁶ As facial recognition technology continues to evolve and become increasingly use by law enforcement, the FBI will need to effectively manage the NGI System.

¹⁸³ "U.S. Gold Refinery Pleads Guilty to Charge of Failure to Maintain Adequate Anti-Money Laundering Program," U.S. Attorney's Office, Southern District of Florida, March 16, 2018, <https://www.justice.gov/usao-sdfl/pr/us-gold-refinery-pleads-guilty-charge-failure-maintain-adequate-anti-money-laundering>.

¹⁸⁴ Kimberly J. Del Greco, "Facial Recognition Technology: Ensuring Transparency in Government Use," Federal Bureau of Investigation, June 4, 2019, <https://www.fbi.gov/news/testimony/facial-recognition-technology-ensuring-transparency-in-government-use>.

¹⁸⁵ Del Greco.

¹⁸⁶ Del Greco.

The FACE Services Unit gives assistance to FBI field offices by comparing pictures of FBI suspects to booking photos of individuals arrested by U.S. law enforcement.¹⁸⁷ The unit uses facial recognition software to compare photos received with images contained in law enforcement databases. The members of the FACE Services Unit manually compare photos of potential matches before providing analysis results to the FBI agent who submitted the request.¹⁸⁸

(2) DNA Analysis

The FBI also uses AI and machine learning in its Combined DNA Index System (CODIS) to support criminal justice DNA databases.¹⁸⁹ Through CODIS, DNA samples from crime scenes are searched against convicted offender and arrestee indices to look for matches.¹⁹⁰ The CODIS tool has had great success helping police identify and prosecute perpetrators of crime that may not otherwise be possible.

Case Examples

A recent example of success includes the arrest and conviction of Jesse Rodriguez who was sentenced to 20 years prison after being convicted of attempted aggravated sexual assault.¹⁹¹ According to the Texas Department of Public Safety, law enforcement was able to match Rodriguez' DNA from a drop of blood he left at the home of a woman when he was cut by the knife he used in attempt to sexually assault her almost 20 years ago. Another recent success was reported by the Washington State Patrol after a suspect's DNA sample was collected from the body of a homicide victim and matched by the CODIS lab to Gary Ault's DNA sample collected in 2014 when he was convicted of a felony for second degree

¹⁸⁷ Del Greco.

¹⁸⁸ Del Greco.

¹⁸⁹ "Frequently Asked Questions on CODIS and NDIS," How We Can Help You, accessed July 13, 2023, <https://www.fbi.gov/how-we-can-help-you/dna-fingerprint-act-of-2005-expungement-policy/codis-and-ndis-fact-sheet>.

¹⁹⁰ Federal Bureau of Investigation.

¹⁹¹ "DNA Helps Convict Attacker Nearly Two Decades Later," Texas Department of Public Safety, January 8, 2024, <https://www.dps.texas.gov/news/dna-helps-convict-attacker-nearly-two-decades-later>.

possession of stolen property.¹⁹² Ault was convicted in March 2024.¹⁹³ CODIS includes the National DNA Index System (NDIS). NDIS uses Expert Systems to efficiently analyze the DNA results.¹⁹⁴ Authorized Expert Systems like GeneMapper ID and TrueAllele use AI and machine learning in their software.¹⁹⁵ With more success stories of bringing homicide and sexual assault victims to justice, continue development of these AI-driven DNA analysis tools will be extremely important.

c. AI Tools Used by Law Enforcement Specific to Financial Crimes

When law enforcement conducts investigations of financial crimes, large volumes of bank documents are received, reviewed and analyzed to identify the placement, layering or integration steps of money laundering being used by criminal organizations. Some sophisticated accounting tools, most notably BankScan, ScanWriter and the Comprehensive Financial Investigative Solution, have been created to reduce the time required to normalize and analyze the bank documents. Prior to the creation of these tools, investigators had to manually input information from bank statements, checks and other financial records into a spreadsheet before they could even begin to do a comprehensive analysis.

(1) BankScan

The tools created to increase efficiency of this process use optical character recognition programs or software. One of the first of these tools is BankScan, created by Gee Whiz Software, LLC.¹⁹⁶ BankScan is used by several federal agencies including HSI, DEA, IRS, and the U.S. Attorney’s Office. It uses OmniPage, an optical character recognition

¹⁹² Washington State Patrol, “2023 CODIS Nwsletter,” Washington State Patrol, accessed April 19, 2024, https://www.wsp.wa.gov/forensics/docs/crimelab/2023_CODIS_Newsletter.pdf.

¹⁹³ Alexandra Duggan and Garrett Cabeza, “Jury Convicts Man of Killing 83-Year-Old Deer Park Man at His Home,” *The Spokesman-Review*, March 29, 2024, <https://www.spokesman.com/stories/2024/mar/29/jury-convicts-man-of-killing-83-year-old-deer-park/>.

¹⁹⁴ Federal Bureau of Investigation, “Frequently Asked Questions on CODIS and NDIS.”

¹⁹⁵ Federal Bureau of Investigation; “GeneMapper™ ID-X Software v1.7, Demo Installation,” ThermoFisher Scientific, accessed July 13, 2023, <https://www.thermofisher.com/order/catalog/product/A71702>; and Mark Perlin, “TrueAllele Process Overview,” video, 8:50, YouTube, May 1, 2013, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=OU29b5sW88Y>.

¹⁹⁶ “About BankScan,” BankScan, accessed July 14, 2023, <https://www.bank-scan.com/content/about-bankscan>.

program, to convert PDF bank and credit card statements into Excel spreadsheets.¹⁹⁷ However, BankScan does require users to manually look for and correct errors, which is a time-consuming process.¹⁹⁸ Although it does not have additional analytical software like its competitors, the basic function saves investigators dozens of hours of processing if they were to manually input account data to a spreadsheet.

An HSI investigation that used the BankScan tool recently resulted in the conviction of Robert Wise, a prominent New York attorney, who provided money laundering services to Viktor Vekselberg, a sanctioned Russian oligarch.¹⁹⁹ Additionally, it resulted in a settlement for violations of Ukraine/Russia-related sanctions. BankScan was frequently used throughout the investigation. Several bank account documents were processed through BankScan to produce a more digestible output to assist in recognizing trends and facilitate tracing of approximately \$3.8 million. These funds were manipulated by Wise to maintain properties owned by Vekselberg in the United States and valued at \$75 million. The BankScan tool aided investigators in creating analytical products that ultimately led to Robert Wise pleading guilty and agreeing to a forfeiture order of \$3.77 million. Analysis through BankScan was also shared with OFAC that yielded a civil settlement of \$466,200 with an insurance company involved in the above-mentioned sanctions violations.²⁰⁰ In summary, the utilization of BankScan not only facilitated the prosecution of Wise but also proved instrumental in enforcing sanctions and combatting financial crime on a broader scale.

¹⁹⁷ BankScan.

¹⁹⁸ BankScan; and Ivan Widjaya, “ScanWriter v. BankScan: Which Data Automation Software Can Simplify Your Life?,” Noobpreneur, March 7, 2022, <https://www.noobpreneur.com/2022/03/07/scanwriter-v-bankscan-which-data-automation-software-can-simplify-your-life/>.

¹⁹⁹ “New York Attorney Pleads Guilty to Conspiring to Commit Money Laundering to Promote Sanctions Violations by Associate of Sanctioned Russian Oligarch,” U.S. Attorney’s Office, Southern District of New York, April 25, 2023, <https://www.justice.gov/usao-sdny/pr/new-york-attorney-pleads-guilty-conspiring-commit-money-laundering-promote-sanctions>.

²⁰⁰ “Settlement Agreement between the U.S. Department of the Treasury’s Office of Foreign Assets Control and Privilege Underwriters Reciprocal Exchange,” Office of Foreign Assets Control, December 21, 2023, https://ofac.treasury.gov/recent-actions/20231221_33.

(2) ScanWriter

ScanWriter is a similar tool with more features created with the implementation of AI and machine learning. ScanWriter processes bank statements, credit card statements, check images, payroll, phone records, general ledgers and other documents into Excel.²⁰¹ The AI and machine learning component of ScanWriter recognizes handwritten notes on check images and automatically adds them to correlating columns in the Excel spreadsheet. The original documents are automatically linked to the data in the spreadsheet. The software supports twenty-one languages and uses AI error detection to ensure accuracy and maximized efficiency.²⁰² It is used by U.S. Treasury, HSI, various state attorney general offices, as well as private accounting firms and other businesses.²⁰³

An example of successful use includes a recent HSI and FBI investigation of insider trading. In October 2021, Michael Shvartsman, Gerald Shvartsman, and Bruce Garelick used their knowledge of a high profile corporate merger between Digital World Acquisition Corporation (DWAC) and a Donald Trump company. They gained over \$22 million by using the non-public information to exchange securities. After signing non-disclosure agreements that restricted them from using confidential information for trading, the trio, including Garelick who was a DWAC board member, exploited their inside knowledge about the merger.²⁰⁴ According to the DOJ press release, they purchased substantial amounts of DWAC securities before the merger announcement and shared this sensitive information with friends and associates, leading to considerable profits for themselves and those they informed once the merger went public. HSI investigators used the ScanWriter tool to convert the bank statements to Excel and then analyze the data to trace funds and identify transactions of money laundering.

²⁰¹ “Data Automation,” ScanWriter, accessed July 14, 2023, <https://scanwriter.personable.com/>.

²⁰² ScanWriter.

²⁰³ ScanWriter.

²⁰⁴ “U.S. Attorney Announces Charges in Four Separate Insider Trading Cases against 10 Individuals, Including Drug Company Employees, Investment Firm Executive Director, and SPAC Investors,” U.S. Attorney’s Office, Southern District of New York, June 29, 2023, <https://www.justice.gov/usao-sdny/pr/us-attorney-announces-charges-four-separate-insider-trading-cases-against-10>.

(3) Comprehensive Financial Investigative Solution

A software with similar features to ScanWriter is Comprehensive Financial Investigative Solution (CFIS), which was created to be used by prosecutors, law enforcement, regulatory agencies and forensic accountants.²⁰⁵ CFIS processes financial documents into spreadsheets and links supporting documents to show the flow of funds. AI intelligent document analyzers process and reconcile statements to ensure accuracy.²⁰⁶ It is used by law enforcement agencies including DEA, Bureau of Alcohol, Tobacco, Firearms and Explosives (ATF), U.S. Secret Service, as well as state and local agencies.²⁰⁷ CFIS, BankScan, and ScanWriter software convert financial documents to manipulative and workable format for analysis. Like ScanWriter, CFIS uses several AI tools to make the analysis more efficient, but in a slightly different way. For example, CFIS does not automatically recognize handwriting and place it into the spreadsheet.

A recent case example of law enforcement using CFIS is in the investigation of Juan Pagan-Reyes, a member of a drug trafficking organization operating in Florida and the Dominican Republic.²⁰⁸ According to the press release, he and his co-conspirators coordinated shipments of cocaine from Colombia and the Dominican Republic to Florida. Pagan-Reyes also arranged for the illicit cash proceeds from the cocaine sales to be laundered and sent to various bank accounts in the U.S. and internationally.²⁰⁹ Pagan-Reyes used third-party money launderers Ronald Vidaurre and Francy Bedoya. Vidaurre and Bedoya lived in Miami, Florida where they incorporated Sofitel Trading Corp., Vibe Enterprise, Inc., and Skyline World Group, Inc. for the purposes of opening business bank accounts used for

²⁰⁵ “CFIS: Comprehensive Financial Investigative Solution Software Product,” Actionable Intelligence Technologies, Inc., accessed July 14, 2023, <https://aitcfis.com/cfis/>.

²⁰⁶ Actionable Intelligence Technologies, Inc.

²⁰⁷ “AIT CFIS Clients,” Actionable Intelligence Technologies, Inc., accessed July 14, 2023, <https://aitcfis.com/clients/>.

²⁰⁸ “Orlando Man Sentenced to over Six Years in Federal Prison for Money Laundering Conspiracy after Being Stopped While Transporting over \$1 Million in Cash,” U.S. Attorney’s Office, Middle District of Florida, October 21, 2022, <https://www.justice.gov/usao-mdfl/pr/orlando-man-sentenced-over-six-years-federal-prison-money-laundering-conspiracy-after>.

²⁰⁹ United States of America v. Jason Pagan-Reyes, No. 8:22cr21KKM-TGW (M.D. Fl. Jan. 12, 2022),

receiving and transferring the narcotics proceeds.²¹⁰ They converted the illicit cash proceeds to cashier's checks addressed to the business accounts and various individuals. DEA investigators used the CFIS tool to analyze thousands of transactions conducted by Pagan-Reyes, Vidaurre, Bedoya to identify other conspirators of the money laundering network and find other bank accounts and assets purchased with the illicit proceeds. By using CFIS to collate and organize the financial data, DEA saw over \$200,000,000 was laundered over a three-year period. Pagan-Reyes, Vidaurre and Bedoya were indicted, charged with money laundering and all plead guilty.²¹¹ The Organized Crime Drug Enforcement Task Force consisting of DEA, IRS-CI, HSI and the Florida Highway Patrol seized houses, businesses, bank accounts and bulk U.S. currency valued at approximately \$20 million.²¹²

(4) Virtual Assets Blockchain Analysis

When law enforcement wants to trace virtual assets, there are options beyond manually searching the blockchain to follow transactions. Tools like Chainalysis and TRM use AI and machine learning to help VASPs and law enforcement monitor, detect and investigate fraud and financial crime.²¹³ Chainalysis has mapped more than 1 billion crypto addresses to real world entities, which is significant in assisting law enforcement corroborate other evidence they have matching suspects to virtual asset transactions.²¹⁴ TRM has capability to trace flow of funds across multiple blockchains within one graph or table.²¹⁵ Law enforcement investigators, analysts and forensic accountants can use both of these tools in tandem to quickly analyze blockchain evidence and create quality infographics for trial

²¹⁰ *United States of America v. Ronald Vidaurre*, No. 8:22cr166VMC-SPF (M.D. Fl. May 6, 2022); *United States of America v. Francly Bedoya*, No. 8:22cr167KKM-AAS (M.D. Fl. May 6, 2022).

²¹¹ *United States of America v. Jason Pagan-Reyes*; *United States of America v. Ronald Vidaurre*; *United States of America v. Francly Bedoya*.

²¹² U.S. Attorney's Office, Middle District of Florida, "Orlando Man Sentenced to over Six Years."

²¹³ "Blockchain Investigations & Risk Management," TRM, accessed July 14, 2023, <https://www.trmlabs.com/>; and "The Blockchain Data Platform," Chainalysis, accessed July 14, 2023, <https://www.chainalysis.com/>.

²¹⁴ "The Blockchain Data Platform."

²¹⁵ TRM Labs, "Blockchain Investigations & Risk Management."

that easily explain the purchase, movement, exchange and conversion of virtual assets conducted by TCOs.

A brilliant example of Chainalysis and TRM virtual asset tracing tools is the investigation of ChipMixer, a darknet servicer that catered to transnational criminal organizations by “mixing” virtual assets as a method to launder illicit proceeds. In March 2023, a joint investigation by HSI and the FBI netted the seizure of internet domains, servers and over \$46 million in virtual assets.²¹⁶ According to the Department of Justice press release on the case, ChipMixer comingled Bitcoin from multiple users in an effort to increase the anonymity of criminal actors. This mixing method made it extremely difficult for law enforcement to trace. Investigators used both Chainalysis and TRM tools to conduct advanced tracing of hundreds of transactions which revealed ChipMixer had laundered over \$3 billion worth of virtual assets across North America, Europe and Asia. The investigation found the third-party money launderer had serviced multiple crimes including ransomware, malware, cyber theft, and pervasive credit card fraud.²¹⁷ With continued cooperation among U.S. and foreign law enforcement partners, virtual asset tracing tools will enhance the ability to take down large scale money laundering activities that occur in the crypto sphere.

C. CONCLUSION

As technology changed to the digitalized era, financial institutions became the caretakers of vast terabytes of data rather than storage rooms of paper documents in filing cabinets. Legal regulation and oversight have encouraged adaptation of new computer tools, including AI machine learning and natural language processing tools that enhance the anti-money laundering programs of financial institutions. No matter what good intentions are behind an innovation, there are always some individuals and organizations that will look to use the innovation for their own selfish means without regard for, or with the explicit intent to harm, others. Criminals are using AI to break a wide array of laws with more efficiency

²¹⁶ “Justice Department Investigation Leads to Takedown of Darknet Cryptocurrency Mixer That Processed over \$3 Billion of Unlawful Transactions,” Office of Public Affairs, March 15, 2023, <https://www.justice.gov/opa/pr/justice-department-investigation-leads-takedown-darknet-cryptocurrency-mixer-processed-over-3>.

²¹⁷ U.S. Department of Justice.

and with more concealment from law enforcement. Law enforcement has responded with using AI tools to resolve cold cases and trace complex layering of virtual assets. There are opportunities for both law enforcement and the financial sector to cooperate in the development and use of AI tools focused on countering money laundering activities.

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IV. CASE STUDIES OF GLOBAL INNOVATION LEADERS: COMPARING AI AND NEW TECH IMPLEMENTATION IN ESTONIA AND THE UAE

This chapter examines case studies of two foreign implementations of AI and evaluates each on the same qualitative criteria: effectiveness, cost, privacy, transparency, and accountability.²¹⁸ First, the chapter summarizes the current threats Estonia and Dubai are facing from TCOs and terrorist organizations. Although some threats differ between the two countries, the U.S. faces all the same threats. Therefore, exploring these threats followed by how each country is using emerging technologies to address those threats is important to the analysis of this thesis. Next, the case studies address government implementation of emerging technology.²¹⁹ The Estonia e-Government was selected for a case study because it is one of the best examples of government adoption of emerging technologies. Estonia is world renowned as a leader in digital government. Its digital ID system and X-Road infrastructure set international standards for how technology can facilitate government operations through decentralized and informal cooperation.²²⁰ The Dubai Police AI policy was selected for review because it has the most comprehensive adoption of AI than any other foreign law enforcement agency. Dubai has been quite successful in accomplishing very ambitious digital transformation goals by forming innovation partnerships between the public and private sectors. Both governments have not only adopted AI technology but have also innovated their implementations, making them compelling examples to study different ways of using AI in government.

The chapter highlights the pros and cons of AI use by governments and examines public concerns for privacy and ethical abuses. It also demonstrates the degree to which Estonia might be a best model for the United States to emulate, while Dubai has a narrower portion of its policy that the U.S. should implement.

²¹⁸ Eisenhardt, “Building Theories from Case Study Research,” 533.

²¹⁹ Yin, *Case Study Research and Applications*, 31.

²²⁰ Paul ‘t Hart, Rainer Kattel, and Ines Mergel, “Estonia’s Digital Transformation,” in *Great Policy Successes*, ed. Mallory Compton (Oxford, UK: Oxford University Press, 2019), 154–57, <https://doi.org/10.1093/oso/9780198843719.001.0001>.

A. ESTONIA E-GOVERNMENT

Estonia, a former member of the Union of the Soviet Socialist Republics, sought to distance and protect itself from Russia after the collapse of the Soviet Union.²²¹ As the Cold War progressed, the Institute of Cybernetics was established in Tallinn, Estonia because computers were needed for submarine hull research.²²² Enn Tyugu claims this institute led computer science among the Soviet Baltic region. Having a well-established computer programming institute dating back to the 1960s, Estonia's information technology (IT) sector wrote a pivotal strategy paper in 1993 that outlined the establishment of modern, inter-connected IT systems.²²³ Meelis Kitsing noted that within a decade, Estonia implemented the X-Road, a government-wide network that allowed all agencies to communicate and access information from multiple databases. The government used the IT backbone to communicate with its citizens through an e-participation portal called Osale to enhance democracy within the country.²²⁴ Estonia became a member of both the European Union (EU) and the North Atlantic Treaty Organization (NATO) in 2004, marking a pivotal milestone in its journey towards integrating with the broader European community.²²⁵

1. Impetus to Strengthen Cyber Security

For Russia, the collapse of the Soviet Union was a great embarrassment. To add insult to injury, countries with significant Russian-speaking populations, like Estonia,

²²¹ Estonia had a long history of suffering under Soviet rule, including severe repression and mass deportations. The Soviet regime attempted to make Estonia more Russian, threatening its cultural identity. Estonia's history of being caught between major powers of Germany and Russia drove the need for strong security measures and alliances with Western nations to solidify its independence. Meike Wulf, *Shadowlands: Memory and History in Post-Soviet Estonia* (New York: Berghahn Books, 2016), ProQuest Ebook Central.

²²² Enn Tyugu, "Computing and Computer Science in the Soviet Baltic Region," in *History of Nordic Computing 2*, ed. John Impagliazzo, Timo Järvi, and Petri Paju (Turku, Finland: Springer, 2009), 13.

²²³ Meelis Kitsing, "Success without Strategy: E-Government Development in Estonia," *Policy & Internet* 3, no. 1 (2011): 5, <https://doi.org/10.2202/1944-2866.1095>.

²²⁴ Maarja Toots, "Why E-Participation Systems Fail: The Case of Estonia's Osale.Ee," *Government Information Quarterly* 36, no. 3 (2019): 547, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.giq.2019.02.002>.

²²⁵ "Estonia," EU member country profile, accessed April 18, 2024, https://european-union.europa.eu/principles-countries-history/country-profiles/estonia_en; "NATO Member Countries," NATO, accessed April 18, 2024, https://www.nato.int/cps/en/natohq/topics_52044.htm.

drifted away from its sphere of influence due to Russia's power decline, which greatly irritated Russia and its leaders including Boris Yeltsin and Vladimir Putin.²²⁶ Tension between Estonia and Russia escalated in 2007 after a controversial statue of a Soviet soldier was moved away from the capital city center. In response, Russia initiated distributed denial of service attacks on the Estonian computer systems.²²⁷ Estonia's Computer Emergency Response Team quickly responded to mitigate the attacks by disconnecting computer services from the world wide web and coordinated with international allies to block over 2,500 internet protocol addresses identified as attacking the Estonian digital infrastructure.²²⁸ Jaan Priisalu and Rain Ottis assert that although Estonia was able to minimize damage through defensive actions, IT architects and government leaders were concerned that there was high potential for large data loss, such as loss of financial transaction data, infiltration of foreign intelligence services and loss of trust in the Estonian IT systems. Thus, cyber security and data privacy became the top priority for Estonia's e-society.

To be sure, Estonians regarded the security of their personal information as paramount in the aftermath of the cyber attacks. During the attacks, the population was not able to access their personal data. Even though no personal data was stolen, due partly to the fact that the Estonian ID card uses a chip and pin for security, the citizens wanted guarantees from their government that their privacy and security would be maintained.²²⁹ As a result, this heightened concern for data security led to the government's commitment

²²⁶ Angela Stent, *Putin's World: Russia against the West and with the Rest* (New York: Twelve Books, 2019), 184.

²²⁷ Distributed Denial of Service attacks prevent users from accessing internet sites by overwhelming the network to reduce users' bandwidth. F. Lau et al., "Distributed Denial of Service Attacks," in *SMC 2000 Conference Proceedings. 2000 IEEE International Conference on Systems, Man and Cybernetics. "Cybernetics Evolving to Systems, Humans, Organizations, and Their Complex Interactions,"* vol. 3, 2000, 2275–80 vol.3, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICSMC.2000.886455>; Priisalu and Ottis, "Personal Control of Privacy and Data," 446.

²²⁸ Kenneth Boyte, "A Comparative Analysis of the Cyberattacks against Estonia, the United States, and Ukraine: Exemplifying the Evolution of Internet-Supported Warfare," *International Journal of Cyber Warfare and Terrorism* 7, no. 2 (2017): 56–57, <https://doi.org/10.4018/IJCWT.2017040104>.

²²⁹ Priisalu and Ottis, "Personal Control of Privacy and Data," 447.

to further strengthen cyber defenses and reassure the public of the robust protection of their personal information.

Estonia took several measures to bolster its cyber security. First, it established the Estonian Information System Authority (EISA). Through legislation, EISA was created to develop and enforce cyber security across all government systems with a centralized approach to protect the national digital infrastructure. Second, the government developed a Cybersecurity Strategy in 2008 that outlined a comprehensive plan to increase its cyber resilience through the creation of legal, strategic and organizational frameworks to address cyber security threats. Third, Estonia expanded its X-Road system across public and private sector databases using sophisticated security measures like authentication, multi-level authorization, and encrypted data traffic to enhance the integrity and security of data transfers. Next, the government invested in public awareness campaigns and education programs to ensure that citizens and organizations were informed about cyber security threats and best practices. Finally, Estonia sought to strengthen international cooperation on cybersecurity, contributing to global standards and learning from the cyber defense experiences of other nations. Today, Peeter Vihma of e-Estonia boasts that “X-Road is implemented in over 20 countries worldwide, and the software is maintained by the Nordic Institute for Interoperability Solutions (NIIS), which consists of Estonia, Finland, and Iceland.”²³⁰ These actions collectively aimed to protect Estonia’s digital infrastructure, prevent future cyber attacks, and build a robust framework for managing and responding to cyber security incidents.

2. Estonia’s Gateway: Transnational Crime Nexus in Northeastern Europe

In Estonia, transnational criminal activities are diverse and encompass various forms of organized crime and cyber threats. TCOs operating in Estonia are predominantly

²³⁰ Peeter Vihma, “The New Frontier: X-Road Launching towards Data Space,” e-Estonia, March 13, 2024, <https://e-estonia.com/the-new-frontier-x-road-launching-towards-data-space/>.

based in Belarus and Russia and are involved in trafficking drugs, people and weapons.²³¹ These criminal organizations take advantage of Estonia's ports and geographical location in northeastern Europe to transit illicit goods and drugs, like cocaine and fentanyl.²³² Lax banking regulations foster financial fraud activity including investment scams and the use of AI large language models (LLMs) to create more convincing messages.²³³ The Organized Crime Index notes that state-sponsored cyber attacks from Russia have been prevalent, but China has recently made significant cyber threats. Estonia reported 484 cyber attacks occurred in 2023, almost 200 more than the previous year.²³⁴ These criminal activities highlight Estonia's ongoing battle with organized crime, influenced by its position as a gateway between East and West Europe.

3. Estonia's AI Strategy

Artificial intelligence is among the fastest growing technologies that is making significant impacts on all sectors of society.²³⁵ Estonia, with its advanced digital framework, embraced development of artificial intelligence. In May 2019 Estonia published a report outlining the country's AI development and implementation strategy, named "Kratt" after a figure from Estonian folklore.²³⁶ The report was written by a working group consisting of government, academic and private sector experts, chaired by Siim Sikkut. The AI Taskforce presented a comprehensive and forward-thinking approach to integrate AI across public and private sectors. Sikkut et.al. established goals of

²³¹ "Criminality in Estonia," Organized Crime Index, accessed July 24, 2024, <https://ocindex.net/>; Rytis Paulauskas, *Baltic Statement at Security Council Open Debate on Transnational Organized Crime – Estonia in UN* (New York: Permanent Mission of Estonia to the UN, 2023), <https://un.mfa.ee/baltic-statement-at-security-council-open-debate-on-transnational-organized-crime/>.

²³² "Estonia," INTERPOL, accessed July 24, 2024, <https://www.interpol.int/Who-we-are/Member-countries/Europe/ESTONIA>.

²³³ Organized Crime Index, "Criminality in Estonia"; Estonia Information System Authority, *Cyber Security in Estonia 2024* (Tallinn, Estonia: Estonia Information System Authority, 2024), 40–41.

²³⁴ Estonia Information System Authority, *Cyber Security in Estonia 2024*, 9–10.

²³⁵ David Autor et al., *An Inclusive Future? Technology, New Dynamics, and Policy Challenges*, May 2022 (Washington, DC: Brookings Institution, 2022), https://www.brookings.edu/wp-content/uploads/2022/05/Inclusive-future_Technology-new-dynamics-policy-challenges.pdf.

²³⁶ e-Estonia, "AI Strategy Factsheet" (e-Estonia, February 2023), <https://e-estonia.com/wp-content/uploads/factsheet-ai-strategy.pdf>.

enhancing public sector efficiency using AI, fostering AI in the private sector to improve competitiveness, elevating research and education in AI, and create legal and ethical frameworks to support AI implementation.²³⁷ With so much of Estonia’s digital infrastructure firmly established on the X-Road, a significant part of the AI strategy revolves around ensuring interoperability between different AI systems and databases to facilitate seamless data exchange, integration and training of AI systems.²³⁸ The AI strategy is designed to be adaptive, with mechanisms for ongoing review and adjustment to incorporate new technologies and methodologies as AI evolves globally.²³⁹ Furthermore, it allows for flexibility to use open source AI solutions as well as solutions developed within the government. Overall, Estonia’s approach to AI underscores a balanced view of accelerating technological adoption while ensuring robust governance, public engagement, and the development of necessary infrastructures to support a sustainable AI ecosystem.

4. Criteria Analysis

As mentioned in the Research Design section of this thesis, each AI policy undergoes an evaluation using five key criteria: effectiveness, cost, privacy, transparency, and accountability. Scores ranging from low to high are assigned to each criterion based on the constraints, challenges, or successes associated with the evaluated policy. An average score is then calculated for each policy, facilitating a comparative analysis with the other AI policies.

a. Effectiveness - High

With 99 percent of its public services online, Estonia is using AI to streamline public interaction with government services, allowing an already efficient government system to improve customer interactions. As of March 2024, over 130 AI projects were

²³⁷ Siim Sikkut et al., *Report of Estonia’s AI Taskforce* (Tallinn, Estonia: Estonian Ministry of Economic Affairs and Communications, 2019).

²³⁸ Sikkut et al., 26.

²³⁹ Sikkut et al., 15,40.

introduced to the Estonian public across different sectors.²⁴⁰ Estonia’s AI Strategy factsheet provides examples of how AI tools are being used to streamline its public services, including Bürokratt, a system of chatbots for government services; systems for detecting tax fraud; self-driving vehicles; robotic transport in hospitals; tailored educational programs for students; translation and text-to-speech technologies; and automated transcription of court and parliamentary proceedings. The ability of Estonia to incorporate open source AI solutions offers flexibility to public services. Due to the well-established use of AI programs in Estonia, the effectiveness is evaluated as high.

Cost - Low

The Estonian AI Strategy aims to increase research and development for AI to 1% of the gross domestic product (GDP).²⁴¹ Estonia’s GDP in 2023 was approximately 27.5 billion euros, meaning the 1 percent GDP goal for AI research and development (R&D) would be 275 million euros for that year.²⁴² In 2023, Minister of Foreign Affairs Margus Tsahkna announced that Estonia would invest 20 million euros (10 percent of the AI R&D budget) in open source, reusable AI building blocks that will be made available to the public, such as Meta’s Llama or Google’s Plan-T5 large language models (LLMs), for example.²⁴³ According to the Open Source Observatory, several European countries are investing in open source AI to compete against U.S. AI companies. Sam Altman, cofounder of US-based OpenAI, told an audience at MIT in July 2023 that the cost of training large language models was over \$100 million.²⁴⁴ By sharing LLM investments with other countries, Estonia can ensure they can increase their IT infrastructure as use of the LLMs increases.

²⁴⁰ “Facts & Figures,” e-Estonia, October 20, 2021, <https://e-estonia.com/facts-and-figures/>.

²⁴¹ Sikkut et al., *Report of Estonia’s AI Taskforce*, 8.

²⁴² “National Accounts,” Statistics Estonia, accessed April 19, 2024, <https://www.stat.ee/en/avasta-statistikat/valdkonnad/rahandus/national-accounts>.

²⁴³ Jaakko Karhu, “Estonia Invests €20 Million into Open Source AI,” Open Source Observatory (OSOR), October 11, 2023, <https://joinup.ec.europa.eu/collection/open-source-observatory-osor/news/estonia-invests-eu20-million-open-source-ai>.

²⁴⁴ Craig S. Smith, “What Large Models Cost You – There Is No Free AI Lunch,” *Forbes*, September 8, 2023, <https://www.forbes.com/sites/craigsmith/2023/09/08/what-large-models-cost-you--there-is-no-free-ai-lunch/>.

In a cost analysis of LLMs by La Javaness R&D, using open source options is more cost effective in the long run over models that require paying for access.²⁴⁵ Figure 3 illustrates the cost projections of both types of LLMs.

Figure 3. Cost Projections of Pay for Service vs. Open Source LLMs²⁴⁶

According to Figure 3, as LLM usage increases, the cost of paying for access increases linearly (blue line) whereas the cost of open source LLMs increases with a flattened curve (tan line). While initial financial investments to integrate open source LLMs cost more, over time the open source tools save money because the pay for service fees continue to increase at a higher rate. By investing in its own infrastructure and sharing investment costs of open source AI with other countries, Estonia is able to make progress in its AI implementation. Therefore, despite the large costs of AI development and maintenance, Estonia’s policy mitigates the burden of its economy by incorporating the private sector and diversifying its AI funding mechanisms. Estonia’s X-Road backbone also allows for AI tools to be quickly incorporated among multiple sectors. Therefore, Estonia’s AI cost is low.

²⁴⁵ “LLM Large Language Model Cost Analysis,” *Medium* (blog), September 29, 2023, <https://lajavaness.medium.com/llm-large-language-model-cost-analysis-d5022bb43e9e>.

²⁴⁶ Adapted from: La Javaness R&D.

b. Privacy - High

The AI Strategy cites both the European Union General Data Protection Regulation and Estonia’s laws that regulate personal data protection for reasons why new legislation is unnecessary when AI is involved as the current legislation is technology-neutral.²⁴⁷ The AI taskforce highlights the fact that using AI to process personal data will be hindered because personal data can only be collected for specific purposes they were originally intended for. It further states that processing personal data beyond the initial purposes is not allowed.

The consideration for privacy within the context of Estonia’s AI strategy is evaluated as high. The strategy explicitly prohibits the use of personal data beyond its initial purposes and references current laws and regulations that protect those privacy concerns. Another reason privacy was rated high is because Estonia citizens personal information was successfully safeguarded during the 2007 cyber attacks, before the IT infrastructure was strengthened and upgraded with more security features.

c. Transparency - High

The Estonian government was open with the public regarding all aspects of the 2007 cyber attacks and their impacts on the infrastructure.²⁴⁸ By not hiding details of the malicious events, the public trusted the government was taking the correct actions to manage what had occurred. Estonia has continued to operate with visible transparency. According to the non-profit organization Freedom House, which advocates for democracy and human rights, Estonia ranks high among the European Union’s governments for openness and transparency.²⁴⁹ For instance, public information is widely available and easily accessible on the e-government website “e-estonia.com.” E-estonia.com provides information on the government’s AI strategy, which includes five ethics principles. One of

²⁴⁷ Sikkut et al., *Report of Estonia’s AI Taskforce*.

²⁴⁸ Priisalu and Ottis, “Personal Control of Privacy and Data,” 447.

²⁴⁹ “Estonia,” *Freedom in the World 2022*, accessed May 29, 2024, <https://freedomhouse.org/country/estonia/freedom-world/2022>.

those five principles is, “The principle of clarity: Act with transparency!”²⁵⁰ Estonians have prioritized trust in the government by ensuring open and clear communication and availability of public information.

Estonia’s e-government website provides the public with information on AI strategy and implementations through downloadable documents and access to podcasts, photos and videos.²⁵¹ The website also provides email and phone options to contact for questions. In 2021, Estonia introduced its AI virtual assistant “Bürokratt” that allows citizens to request government services and information through chat, text, email, or phone. According to Estonia’s AI Strategy, one of the main focuses is enhancing AI literacy by ensuring citizens are well-informed and are active participants.²⁵² Due to these successes, transparency was evaluated as “high.”

d. Accountability - High

Members of the AI Strategy taskforce recognized Estonian AI tools have the potential to be used by individuals in a manner that could threaten property or the environment. They suggested new laws be proposed to ensure such acts are punishable as criminal. The updated Kratt Strategy of 2022–2023 affirmed an AI regulation was drafted but was aborted after the European Commission introduced an EU-wide regulation on AI.²⁵³ Estonia is actively participating in the development of European legal frameworks that regulate AI. By ensuring AI initiatives are developed ethically with respect to fundamental human rights, Estonia’s accountability is evaluated as high.

5. Summary

Estonia has led a remarkable journey over the past couple of decades as a pioneer of technological advancement and adoption. The limited impact of Russian cyber attacks

²⁵⁰ Sikkut et al., *Report of Estonia’s AI Taskforce*, 42.

²⁵¹ e-Estonia, “Facts & Figures.”

²⁵² E-Estonia, “AI Strategy: Factsheet,” March 3, 2024, <https://e-estonia.com/wp-content/uploads/factsheet-ai-strategy-march-2024-3.pdf>.

²⁵³ Sikkut et al., *Report of Estonia’s AI Taskforce*, 40.

demonstrated how robust Estonia’s digital infrastructure was, which has increased in cyber defense and security. The interoperability of its digital backbone has welcomed AI innovations across all government sectors. The small European country actively invests its funds and expertise into not only Estonia AI development, but also the European community, which provides reciprocal benefits. The AI strategy is evaluated as “high” across effectiveness, privacy, transparency and accountability; and evaluated as “low” for cost.

B. DUBAI: WITH AN EMPHASIS ON THE AI

Dubai is one of seven emirates that together encompass the United Arab Emirates (UAE), a federation of monarchies.²⁵⁴ Understanding that Dubai had limited oil reserves, Sheikh Rashid Bin Saeed Al Maktoum led Dubai’s diversification of its economy with emphasis on trade, finance and tourism since the establishment of the UAE in 1971.²⁵⁵ According to Michael Matly and Laura Dillon, Dubai’s focus on trade not only improved its economy but also fostered openness to foreign thoughts and culture. In 2000, Dubai opened a business park specific to the internet which attracted computer powerhouses like Microsoft and IBM.²⁵⁶ These steps paved the way for the future of Dubai to embrace AI.

1. Forward Leaning

In 2021, Sheikh Mohammed Bin Rashid Al Maktoum (grandson of Sheikh Rashid Bin Saeed Al Maktoum) established Digital Dubai with the vision of making Dubai a leading digital economy—not just regionally, but globally.²⁵⁷ Digital Dubai’s home page states that it was established to develop and implement strategies and policies regarding Dubai’s cyber-security, data, information technology, and digital transformation. With the help of long-time private partner IBM, Dubai created its own Artificial Intelligence Lab in

²⁵⁴ “United Arab Emirates,” The World Factbook, June 11, 2024, <https://www.cia.gov/the-world-factbook/countries/united-arab-emirates/>.

²⁵⁵ Michael Matly and Laura Dillon, “Dubai Strategy: Past, Present, Future” (Harvard Business School, February 27, 2007), 1–2, https://www.belfercenter.org/sites/default/files/legacy/files/matly_paper1.pdf.

²⁵⁶ Matly and Dillon, 3.

²⁵⁷ “Digital Dubai Home Page,” Digital Dubai, accessed July 4, 2024, <https://www.digitaldubai.ae>.

furtherance of the Digital Dubai strategies to make the city more efficient and impactful.²⁵⁸ The AI Lab states its four principles are ethics, security, humanity and inclusiveness. By embracing cutting-edge technologies and prioritizing ethical considerations, Dubai aims to set a global benchmark for smart city initiatives, enhancing the quality of life for its residents and visitors while fostering sustainable economic growth.

The Dubai AI Principles and Ethics guidelines constitute a hybrid strategy that integrates local and global perspectives. While it is rooted in achieving Dubai-specific goals, it also emphasizes the importance of aligning with international standards and engaging in global cooperation.²⁵⁹ Furthermore, the guidelines stress the importance of sharing the benefits of AI across society. Because Dubai approaches AI implementation with consideration of the global community, it is worth reviewing and evaluating how Dubai has implemented AI to its police force for the purpose of exploring ways U.S. law enforcement can use AI to combat money laundering.

2. Dubai Crime Picture

Dubai's extensive financial infrastructure, numerous free trade zones, cash-intensive economy, and minimal money laundering prosecutions make it a target for professional money laundering networks.²⁶⁰ As a major trading hub, money launderers and terrorist financiers utilize trade-based money laundering methods to move funds through Dubai.²⁶¹ The extensive illicit activity is reflected in the UAE's efforts to combat it, with the conviction of 75 individuals for terrorist financing from 2013 through 2019.²⁶² The Financial Action Task Force Mutual Evaluation Report of the UAE stated cybercriminals engage in fraud linked to larger TCOs through the advanced digital

²⁵⁸ "AI Lab," Digital Dubai, accessed July 4, 2024, <https://www.digitaldubai.ae/initiatives/ai-lab>.

²⁵⁹ "Artificial Intelligence Principles & Ethics," Digital Dubai, accessed July 4, 2024, <https://www.digitaldubai.ae/initiatives/ai-principles-ethics>.

²⁶⁰ Financial Action Task Force, *Mutual Evaluation Report of the United Arab Emirates* (Paris, France: Financial Action Task Force, 2020), <https://www.fatf-gafi.org/content/dam/fatf-gafi/mer/Executive-Summary-Mutual-Evaluation-Report-UAE-2020.pdf>.

²⁶¹ Financial Action Task Force, 6.

²⁶² Financial Action Task Force, 9.

infrastructure in Dubai. TCOs take advantage of the trade industry to transit illicit drugs through the UAE.²⁶³ Dubai's position as a global financial and trading hub, combined with its advanced digital infrastructure, makes it a prime target for a variety of illegal activities conducted by TCOs and terrorist financiers.

3. Dubai Policing AI Strategy

With threats posed by regional conflicts and militant groups, Dubai has intensified its efforts to ensure security through advanced AI technologies. The Smart Dubai AI Principles & Ethics guidelines provide two examples regarding AI technology being used for border security for the purposes of identifying suspicious activity, implying a strong desire to protect residents and visitors of Dubai and the UAE.²⁶⁴ In January of 2022, the Shi'a Muslim Houthi group in Yemen, backed by Iran, sent missiles and drones to Abu Dhabi and Dubai infrastructure that killed three people.²⁶⁵ According to a U.S. Department of State travel advisory issued in July, 2023, the UAE continue to face ongoing threats from militant groups in Yemen.²⁶⁶ Counter-terrorism is one of the main securitization factors claimed by Dubai Police for their AI implementation projects.

In 2018, the Dubai Police announced an AI strategic plan that aimed to simplify police services for the public and make Dubai a safe city by using AI in all areas of policing, including traffic accidents, security, and crime forecasting.²⁶⁷ A police convention hosted by Dubai in March of 2023 showcased some of the new AI tools the Dubai Police had

²⁶³ Financial Action Task Force, *MER of the UAE*.

²⁶⁴ Digital Dubai, "Artificial Intelligence Principles & Ethics," 15,23.

²⁶⁵ Ghaida Ghantous and Alexander Cornwell, "U.S. Condemns Deadly Houthi Attack on Abu Dhabi; UAE Reserves Right to Respond," Reuters, January 17, 2022, <https://www.reuters.com/world/middle-east/uae-says-suspects-drones-behind-abu-dhabi-fires-yemens-houthis-claim-attack-2022-01-17/>.

²⁶⁶ "United Arab Emirates Travel Advisory," U.S. Department of State, accessed July 12, 2024, <https://travel.state.gov/content/travel/en/traveladvisories/traveladvisories/united-arab-emirates-travel-advisory.html>.

²⁶⁷ Bhunia, "Dubai Police Releases 2018–31 Strategic Plan for Artificial Intelligence"; Amira Agarib, "Dubai Police Adopt Strategic AI Plan," *Khaleej Times*, December 22, 2017, <https://www.khaleejtimes.com/uae/dubai-police-adopt-strategic-ai-plan>.

implemented and were available for sale by the developers.²⁶⁸ Among the technologies on display at the event were different facial recognition software that analyze a person's mood based on facial expressions or track individuals across cities through vast camera networks.²⁶⁹ Dubai police also explained a predictive tool they developed with machine learning pinpoints where theft might occur with an accuracy rate of 68 percent.²⁷⁰ Officials of the Emirates' Mission of the Interior showed that after capturing images of attendees' irises on a tablet they were able to pull up UAE border crossing information and associated photos of those individuals.²⁷¹ These advancements demonstrate Dubai's commitment to leverage AI technology to enhance security measures and improve efficiency in policing.

4. Criteria Analysis

Each AI policy undergoes an evaluation using five key criteria: effectiveness, cost, privacy, transparency, and accountability. Scores ranging from low to high are assigned to each criterion based on the constraints, challenges, or successes associated with the evaluated policy. An average score is then calculated for each policy, facilitating a comparative analysis with the other AI policies.

a. Effectiveness – High

A 2021 peer-review study found that innovation and strategic planning are the most important factors for improving the organizational performance of the Dubai Police.²⁷² The success of the innovation strategy is exemplified by the enhancement of 29

²⁶⁸ Paul Mozur and Adam Satariano, "A.I., Brain Scans and Cameras: The Spread of Police Surveillance Tech," *New York Times*, March 30, 2023, sec. Technology, <https://www.nytimes.com/2023/03/30/technology/police-surveillance-tech-dubai.html>.

²⁶⁹ Mozur and Satariano.

²⁷⁰ Mozur and Satariano.

²⁷¹ Mozur and Satariano.

²⁷² Mohammed Saleh Alosani, Rushami Yusoff, and Hassan Al-Dhaafri, "The Effect of Innovation and Strategic Planning on Enhancing Organizational Performance of Dubai Police," *Innovation & Management Review* 17, no. 1 (2020): 10,15, <https://doi.org/10.1108/INMR-06-2018-0039>.

administrative operations through AI integration.²⁷³ Significant AI tools include analysis of minor accidents (eliminating human interaction for accident reports), a virtual officer app (allows the public receive answers to questions via voice commands in Arabic or English), and a smart police station (offers 70 services in seven languages and has processed over 36,000 transactions since the beginning of 2024), according to the Emirates News Agency. Dubai Police Colonel Rashed Bin Dhaboui reported that crime rates in 2023 had decreased by 25 percent compared to the same period in 2022 due to AI technology used to predict crime.²⁷⁴ Not only have crime rates decreased, but so has the time it takes to solve crimes in Dubai. AI algorithms now assist in virtual autopsies to determine if an actual autopsy is needed, and, if so, identify specific organs a doctor should examine.²⁷⁵ Major General Ahmed Thani bin Ghalita Al Muhairi, the Director of the General Department of Criminal Evidence and Criminology claimed that it takes ten days for Dubai police to solve a crime, compared to 35 days in the United States.²⁷⁶ Overall, the AI integration strategy has proven to be highly effective with numerous transformative tools having been introduced that enhance the operational efficiency of the Dubai Police.

b. Cost – High

As of March 2024, the largest investment made in the Dubai Police AI strategy has been the construction of a state-of-the-art facility, costing 550 million Dirhams, which is equivalent to approximately 150 million U.S. dollars.²⁷⁷ The government also announced rewards for top computer programming students of more than \$1 million, on top of offering

²⁷³ Amjad Saleh, “Dubai Police Integrates AI into 29 Administrative Operations,” Emirates News Agency, June 12, 2024, <https://www.wam.ae/en/article/b3mmufi-dubai-police-integrates-into-administrative>.

²⁷⁴ “Dubai Police Reports Significant Decrease in Crime Rates in Q1 2023,” Emirates News Agency, April 30, 2023, <https://www.wam.ae/en/article/hszrgyi4-dubai-police-reports-significant-decrease-crime>.

²⁷⁵ Waad Barakat, “Dubai: Autopsy in 5 Minutes; How Police Are Using AI to Solve Crimes Faster,” *Khaleej Times*, March 5, 2024, <https://www.khaleejtimes.com/uae/dubai-autopsy-in-5-minutes-how-police-are-using-ai-to-solve-crimes-faster>.

²⁷⁶ Barakat.

²⁷⁷ Barakat; “550 Million AED to USD - UAE Dirham to U.S. Dollar,” Currency Converter X, accessed July 13, 2024, <https://www.currencyconverterx.com/AED/USD/550000000>.

free training.²⁷⁸ The UAE pledged to invest one billion Dirhams (approximately \$270 million) at the onset of its AI development strategy.²⁷⁹ With more of a focus on developing custom AI tools and infrastructure to support them, the cost of developing AI technology for the Dubai police is high.

c. Privacy –Low

The Dubai AI Ethics Principles and Guidelines document states that individual privacy should be respected, and personal information should be protected.²⁸⁰ Even though the policy discourages AI surveillance that violates accepted standards of privacy, the way the policy is written is vague.²⁸¹ As an authoritarian government, Dubai and the UAE are able to make unilateral decisions without input from the public. Often UAE rulers, like other autocratic rulers, make decisions that strengthen their own power at the expense of others. According to Freedom House, the UAE has held political prisoners without due process and charged them as terrorists.²⁸² It is likely the UAE authorities are using their advanced AI technologies to monitor political opponents.²⁸³ Although Dubai’s AI strategy states privacy should be protected, it does not mandate the protection or define the extent of privacy protections. Therefore, the privacy aspect of Dubai Police’s AI strategy is evaluated as low.

²⁷⁸ Mohanad Halaweh, “Viewpoint: Artificial Intelligence Government (Gov. 3.0): The UAE Leading Model,” *Journal of Artificial Intelligence Research* 62 (2018): 269–72, <https://doi.org/10.1613/jair.1.11210>.

²⁷⁹ Shabin Basheer, “AED 1 Billion Investment in Pipeline for Projects and Companies Taking Part in Dubai Future Accelerators,” Dubai Future Foundation, August 2, 2016, <https://www.dubaifuture.ae/latest-news/aed-1-billion-investment-in-pipeline-for-projects-and-companies-taking-part-in-dubai-future-accelerators/>; “1 Billion United Arab Emirates Dirhams to U.S. Dollars Exchange Rate: Convert AED/USD,” Wise, accessed July 13, 2024, <https://wise.com/us/currency-converter/aed-to-usd-rate?amount=1000000000>.

²⁸⁰ Smart Dubai, *AI Ethics Principles & Guidelines* (Dubai Digital Authority), 11, accessed July 5, 2024, <https://www.digitaldubai.ae/initiatives/ai-principles-ethics>.

²⁸¹ Smart Dubai, 11.

²⁸² “United Arab Emirates,” Freedom in the World 2024, accessed July 10, 2024, <https://freedomhouse.org/country/united-arab-emirates/freedom-world/2024>.

²⁸³ Freedom House.

d. Transparency - Low

Information on the Dubai Police AI strategy and implementation is only superficially accessible on the Dubai government website. The information reported through the media do not include details describing how AI tools work. The AI Ethics Principles & Guidelines suggest AI tools be developed with the ability to trace how decisions within the system are made.²⁸⁴ However, the section regarding transparency has caveat phrases like, “should consider building in,” and, “where possible.”²⁸⁵ The lack of detailed AI development information publicly available coupled with the weak transparency guidelines garner a low evaluation.

e. Accountability - Moderate

Dubai’s AI policy emphasizes the importance of accountability, though it places the onus on the designers, developers, and the users of AI systems rather than on the overseeing body.²⁸⁶ The preamble of Dubai’s AI Ethics document states, “The Smart Dubai Office will not be responsible for any misuse of the AI Ethics Principles and Guidelines,” which could potentially leave room for non-ethical exploitation.²⁸⁷ By not taking full ownership of new AI technologies it helps create, Dubai shifts accountability to those directly involved in the creation and use of these systems. However, the policy also stresses that these systems should be developed by diverse teams, which can enhance ethical oversight and reduce biases.²⁸⁸ Although this strategy can promote responsibility among stakeholders, the lack of direct accountability from the overseeing body can be seen as a weakness in the policy’s structure. Therefore, accountability is evaluated as moderate.

²⁸⁴ Smart Dubai, *AI Ethics*, 27.

²⁸⁵ Smart Dubai, 27.

²⁸⁶ Smart Dubai, 7.

²⁸⁷ Smart Dubai, 4.

²⁸⁸ Smart Dubai, 7.

5. Summary

Dubai’s conscious decision to diversify its economy led to decades-long relationships with high-tech businesses. The forward vision of its leaders primed the collaborative efforts of all-in AI development to improve government functions and act as a global innovation leader. The Dubai Police have implemented dozens of new AI technologies to their security and administrative functions in a few short years. The AI strategy is evaluated as “high” for effectiveness and cost, “moderate” for accountability, and “low for privacy and transparency.

C. COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS

This section consists of a comparative analysis of the AI initiatives undertaken by the Estonian government and the Dubai Police. By examining the strategic implementation, ethical considerations, and overall effectiveness of these AI programs, the analysis aims to identify the strengths and weaknesses inherent in each approach. This analysis will provide valuable insights into how different governmental bodies leverage AI technologies to enhance public services and address security concerns. Through this comparative lens, a better understanding can be gained for how AI is applied in public administration and the varying outcomes of these initiatives. The purpose of this comparative analysis is to determine which strategies and considerations from other governments should be implemented in the U.S. AI strategy.

The AI strategies of both Estonia and Dubai are highly effective. Interestingly, they rank different in the other evaluation categories of cost, privacy, transparency, and accountability. Table 3 gives a visual matrix of how the two AI strategies compare to each other in each category. The analysis displayed in Table 3 indicates distinct differences among the AI strategies. The pros and cons of AI implementation by these two governments are made clear through the following comparisons.

Table 3. Comparing Estonia’s and Dubai’s AI Strategies

Comparative Analysis		
Category	Estonia	Dubai
Effectiveness	High	High
Cost	Low	High
Privacy	High	Low
Transparency	High	Low
Accountability	High	Moderate

1. Effectiveness

Both Estonia and Dubai have leveraged AI technologies to enhance their public services and governmental operations. Estonia was able to seamlessly introduce 130 AI technologies across various public sectors by implementing them through the pre-existing e-government platform.²⁸⁹ The AI introductions greatly increased the efficiency of public services. Likewise, Dubai has also implemented numerous AI tools to its government services. The Dubai Police introduced AI technologies to improve twenty-nine administrative operations which made them more efficient.²⁹⁰ Since using the AI tools, Dubai police claim significant decreases in crime rates and less time to solve crimes.²⁹¹ It is clear that through different approaches, Estonia and Dubai were able to create and execute very effective AI strategies.

2. Cost

Although Estonia and Dubai pledged similar amounts AI research and development, they used different funding tactics in their AI strategies. Estonia made an

²⁸⁹ e-Estonia, “Facts & Figures.”

²⁹⁰ Saleh, “Dubai Police Integrates AI into 29 Administrative Operations.”

²⁹¹ Emirates News Agency, “Dubai Police Reports Significant Decrease”; Barakat, “Dubai.”

initial goal to invest approximately \$300 million compared to the UAE’s initial investment of \$270 million.²⁹² While Estonia clearly publicizes its spending on AI, Dubai does not publicly announce its spending for all AI projects. Estonia shares investments to AI LLMs with other countries to reduce their costs while sharing the benefits with others.²⁹³ The fact that Estonia already had the digital backbone across its government allowed the new AI tools to quickly be incorporated. Conversely, Dubai worked on developing AI tools as it also paid for new infrastructure to support the AI strategy.²⁹⁴ Even though the UAE already had strong working relationships with tech companies like IBM and Microsoft, the government offered millions of dollars of free training and bonuses to attract highly qualified computer programming students.²⁹⁵ Dubai also focuses on developing more AI tools from the ground up whereas Estonia incorporates open-source AI to save costs and decrease the time spent on development. These differing approaches illustrate how Estonia and Dubai have tailored their AI strategies to their unique circumstances, leveraging existing strengths and addressing specific challenges to achieve their goals.

3. Privacy

The approaches to privacy in AI strategies vary significantly between Estonia and Dubai. Estonian and EU laws protect individual privacy, even as new AI technologies are developed and added to Estonia’s government offices.²⁹⁶ The AI strategy forged by Estonia makes it clear that personal data and privacy will be protected. While Estonia’s AI strategy explicitly prohibits misuse of personal data and creates protections, the Dubai AI Ethics and Principles merely offer suggestions to respect and protect personal

²⁹² Sikkut et al., *Report of Estonia’s AI Taskforce*, 8; “Convert EUR to USD: Euro To U.S. Dollar Exchange Rates,” Exchange-Rates, accessed July 15, 2024, <https://www.exchange-rates.org/converter/eur-usd>; Basheer, “AED 1 Billion Investment in Pipeline for Projects and Companies Taking Part in Dubai Future Accelerators”; “1 Billion United Arab Emirates Dirhams to U.S. Dollars Exchange Rate: Convert AED/USD.”

²⁹³ Karhu, “Estonia Invests €20 Million into Open Source AI”; La Javaness R&D, “LLM Large Language Model Cost Analysis.”

²⁹⁴ Currency Converter X, “550 Million AED to USD.”

²⁹⁵ Halaweh, “Viewpoint.”

²⁹⁶ Sikkut et al., *Report of Estonia’s AI Taskforce*.

information.²⁹⁷ Dubai Police proudly promote their advanced surveillance capabilities without explaining how it is used and on whom. Estonia’s AI vision truly reflects its commitment to protecting privacy whereas Dubai’s AI strategy considers privacy more as an afterthought – considering the authoritarian nature of the government – that should be mentioned to appease the international community.

4. Transparency

Transparency in AI development and implementation is a crucial factor in building public trust and understanding. AI machine learning models are very complex, making it difficult to interpret their decision-making processes.²⁹⁸ Recognizing this challenge, Estonia’s AI strategy focuses on teaching AI literacy to its public while also making information on government AI strategy and projects easily accessible.²⁹⁹ The stark distinction with Dubai lies in the fact that government AI strategy facts are not fully provided to the public. Most of the information provided to the public comes from government officials speaking with the media – local media is owned and operated by the state and international media is only granted access to information the state wants to divulge.³⁰⁰ Estonia does a commendable job ensuring AI developments are understandable and communicated with the public, but individuals in Dubai are left in the dark. When a government hides security practices from the population, like Dubai does with its AI surveillance technologies, it is able to use those tools against the population to maintain its power.³⁰¹ Therefore, the contrast between Estonia’s openness and Dubai’s secrecy highlights the importance of considering how to mitigate ethical concerns when implementing emerging technologies.

²⁹⁷ Smart Dubai, *AI Ethics*, 6.

²⁹⁸ Dattatray Vishnu Kute et al., “Deep Learning and Explainable Artificial Intelligence Techniques Applied for Detecting Money Laundering-A Critical Review,” *IEEE Access* 9 (2021): 2, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2021.3086230>.

²⁹⁹ e-Estonia, “Facts & Figures”; E-Estonia, “AI Strategy: Factsheet.”

³⁰⁰ Freedom House, “United Arab Emirates.”

³⁰¹ Daniel J. Solove, *Nothing to Hide: The False Tradeoff between Privacy and Security* (New Haven, CT: Yale University Press, 2011), 24–29, <https://papers.ssrn.com/abstract=3976770>.

5. Accountability

Ethical development and accountability are key components to effective AI strategies. Estonia ensures AI initiatives are developed ethically by creating new laws that ensure harmful use of AI tools are punished as criminal offenses.³⁰² Dubai's AI policy does emphasize that accountability is important, but puts the responsibility on the designers, developers and users of the system without including the overseeing government institution.³⁰³ Therefore, Dubai's AI strategy is evaluated lower than Estonia's AI strategy in terms of ethical oversight and accountability. These differences underscore the importance of a comprehensive approach to accountability in ensuring ethical use of AI technologies.

D. CONCLUSION

The comparative analysis of Estonia's and Dubai's AI strategies reveals significant differences in their approaches to implementation, funding, transparency, and accountability. Estonia and Dubai face similar threats from TCOs drug trafficking and financial fraud. Dubai faces a higher terrorist threat than Estonia but does not encounter the same level of cyber attacks. While both countries have developed effective AI strategies that enhance public services and governmental operations, Estonia stands out for its strong emphasis on privacy protections, transparency, and ethical accountability. Conversely, Dubai excels in rapid AI deployment and innovative applications, albeit with lower transparency and privacy standards as it is an authoritarian government. These insights highlight the importance of a balanced AI strategy that combines robust ethical frameworks with technological innovation. As the United States refines its AI strategy, incorporating the strengths and addressing the weaknesses observed in Estonia and Dubai's approaches could lead to a more comprehensive and effective AI policy framework.

³⁰² Sikkut et al., *Report of Estonia's AI Taskforce*, 40.

³⁰³ Smart Dubai, *AI Ethics*, 7.

V. CONCLUSION

The implementation of AI has improved efficiency and effectiveness in numerous applications. These advanced technologies are not inherently good or bad, but they are open to malicious or benevolent use depending on who operates them. In the realm of financial crimes, TCOs are using AI to enhance their financial fraud and money laundering capabilities. Law enforcement has begun to incorporate AI to anti-money laundering efforts but need to do more to significantly counter TCOs.

Cybersecurity firm SlashNext claimed that malicious emails sent to defraud individuals and businesses has increased significantly since the release of ChatGPT.³⁰⁴ Prior to LLMs like ChatGPT, most of the emails sent to trick people into sending money were written in broken English with poor grammar, signaling to the recipient the email was likely a scam. Emails produced with the assistance of LLMs appear much more legitimate and convincing.³⁰⁵ Although ChatGPT and other generative AI tools are being built with guardrails to keep legitimate use, criminals are finding ways around those guardrails and sharing that hacking knowledge within the broader criminal world.³⁰⁶ TCOs could manipulate LLMs to come up with new money laundering methods that could go unnoticed by law enforcement for years.

A. RECOMMENDATIONS

This thesis recommends three key strategies to amplify the U.S.'s anti-money laundering initiatives against TCOs, which pose serious threats to both national and global financial systems. First, it advocates for the creation of a single digital infrastructure to unify all federal data, enhancing rapid deployment and integration of AI technologies. Second, it proposes fostering mutually beneficial collaboration between the public, private

³⁰⁴ SlashNext, "State of Phishing," May 17, 2024, <https://slashnext.com/the-state-of-phishing-2024/>.

³⁰⁵ Bob Violino, "AI Tools Such as ChatGPT Are Generating a Mammoth Increase in Malicious Phishing Emails," CNBC, November 28, 2023, <https://www.cnbc.com/2023/11/28/ai-like-chatgpt-is-creating-huge-increase-in-malicious-phishing-email.html>.

³⁰⁶ Violino.

and academic sectors. Third, it recommends a specialized AI policy tailored for DHS law enforcement agencies to advance criminal enforcement and investigations. The final recommendation provides potential tools for the future. These recommendations propose to streamline technology use across government sectors, ensure robust cybersecurity, and improve overall law enforcement effectiveness against complex global crimes.

1. Single Digital Infrastructure

The United States government should create a unified digital backbone that would integrate all federal agencies' data and services into a single platform. This centralization will significantly enhance the government's ability to rapidly deploy new technologies, particularly in the realm of artificial intelligence. By having a single digital infrastructure, the U.S. can ensure that new AI tools and technologies are implemented efficiently across various governmental sectors without the need to navigate through the complexities of disparate systems.

A central feature of this unified system would be its robust cybersecurity framework. Estonia's X-Road is particularly noted for its regular updates and fortifications that protect against potential cyber threats. Adopting a similar approach, the U.S. system would be designed to continuously update and strengthen its cyber defenses, thereby eliminating many of the vulnerabilities that plague fragmented systems. This unified coordination not only secures sensitive government data but also ensures the integrity and reliability of services provided to the public.

To successfully implement a centralized digital infrastructure similar to Estonia's X-Road across U.S. federal agencies, the strategy should begin with a thorough initial assessment to evaluate current digital systems and their integration capabilities. Following this assessment, a robust and scalable framework should be developed to make sure it supports seamless data exchange and interoperability among agencies. A pilot program should then be launched within select agencies to test the system's functionality and gather insights, which would inform any necessary adjustments to the technical specifications. Once proven effective, the infrastructure could be rolled out gradually to all federal agencies, with comprehensive support to manage the transition. A dedicated team should

be established to continuously monitor and improve the infrastructure, focusing on implementing advanced cybersecurity measures and updating the technology as needed. This systematic approach will modernize the U.S. government’s information technology infrastructure, streamline service delivery, and enhance security.

2. AI Integration through Partnerships

Organizational responses to AI-enabled malicious activities have varied. Private sector pursues profits from AI advancements but recognizes potential for misuse by malicious actors. Public sector entities focus more on safety for mankind. Some nation leaders agitate for international cohesion and have attempted collaborative approaches with the private industry. The end of this section explains how various private and public organizations are incorporating AI and creating partnerships while acknowledging vital ethical and privacy concerns.

Stanford University’s 2023 review of emerging technologies (SETR) highlighted beneficial and malicious impacts of AI machine learning.³⁰⁷ The report states that risk management is the most significant challenge of novel AI advancements, because users do not have a thorough understanding of the new AI tools’ risks. For example, the SETR observes that the U.S. Department of Defense process to integrate AI to military capabilities is purposefully slow to minimize risk. It further claims that although numerous governments are creating AI regulations, “research on foundational AI technologies is difficult if not impossible to regulate” because other nations will continue advancing AI on their own regardless of regulations implemented by the U.S.³⁰⁸ During an interview with the Financial Times, Stanford computer scientist Fei-Fei Li expressed concern about the state of AI in the academic realm when she said that due to a lack of resources within academic AI, the primary area of research of AI is driven by the private sector.³⁰⁹ Li claims

³⁰⁷ Condoleezza Rice et al., *The Stanford Emerging Technology Review 2023: A Report on Ten Key Technologies and Their Policy Implications* (Stanford, CA: Stanford University, 2023), 20–30, <https://setr.stanford.edu/>.

³⁰⁸ Rice et al., 28.

³⁰⁹ George Hammond, “AI Scientist Fei-Fei Li: ‘Maths Is Pretty Clean. Humans Are Messy,’” *Financial Times*, December 15, 2023, <https://www.ft.com/content/d5f91c27-3be8-454a-bea5-bb8ff2a85488>.

the private sector is focused on improving productivity while universities and the public sector strive to develop AI with the purpose of helping humanity. Therefore, as the literature reveals, developing AI for the purpose of increasing revenue could present more risks to humanity because there is less emphasis on minimizing risk.

Matteo E. Bonfanti contrasts Li’s opinion by claiming that both private companies and public entities contribute to cyber security by advancing AI through their own pursuits.³¹⁰ He noted that although it is true that private sector AI development is driven by profit, governments have collaborated with the private sector to create guiding principles that take overall safety of humanity into consideration, and therefore public risks are being addressed.³¹¹ After consulting with over 500 stakeholders, including prominent private sector AI developers, the European Commission proposed the Artificial Intelligence Act to regulate AI development.³¹² The European Commission would like to prohibit certain AI practices that would manipulate human behavior and impose strict regulations on high-risk AI systems that could cause significant harm.³¹³ Until these laws are passed and enforced, it is unclear how well government regulation will ensure safety as AI development progresses.

Governments can influence the private industry, according to strategic AI researchers Joe O’Brien, Shaun Ee, and Zoe Williams. They noted that after U.S. President Joe Biden met with some of the most prominent AI developers, those private entities agreed

³¹⁰ Matteo E. Bonfanti, “Artificial Intelligence and the Offense–Defense Balance in Cyber Security,” in *Cyber Security Politics: Socio-Technological Transformations and Political Fragmentation*, ed. Myriam Dunn Cavely and Andreas Wenger (Abingdon, UK: Taylor & Francis, 2022), 67–68, <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003110224>.

³¹¹ Bonfanti, “AI and Balance in Cyber Security”; and European Commission, *Building Trust in Human-Centric Artificial Intelligence* (Brussels, Belgium: European Commission, 2019), <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/communication-building-trust-human-centric-artificial-intelligence>.

³¹² European Commission, *Building Trust in Human-Centric Artificial Intelligence*; and European Commission, “Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council Laying Down Harmonised Rules on Artificial Intelligence (Artificial Intelligence Act) and Amending Certain Union Legislative Acts,” EUR-Lex, April 21, 2021, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:52021PC0206>.

³¹³ European Commission, “Proposal of Artificial Intelligence Act.”

to share information on trends of malicious AI users as well as best safety practices.³¹⁴ According to the White House, seven AI companies agreed to ensure products were safe before releasing them to the public, building safe systems with cybersecurity and insider threat safeguards, and developing public trust through transparency.³¹⁵ These companies agreed to include testing by independent experts to mitigate security risks.³¹⁶ O'Brien et al. highlight that Google, Microsoft, OpenAI and Anthropic created the Frontier Model Forum in furtherance of the goals established during the meeting with Biden.³¹⁷ The Frontier Model Forum website has indicated that the organization is in the process of setting up an advisory board that will steer its strategic direction and priority areas.³¹⁸ Additionally, it will create a charter, secure financial resources, and form an executive board dedicated to spearheading initiatives that tackle issues related to AI, including risk management, standardization, and societal impact.³¹⁹ Commitments from AI companies to partner with public sectors show promise that privacy and security concerns will be adequately addressed, as long as those private entities follow through with their affirmations.

The Frontier Model Forum is a great example of cooperation among the private sector, with some influence by the public sector, to create AI tools with the public good as a priority. However, academia must also be included. Universities have the experts required to improve AI, but they are not profit driven like private businesses. The U.S. should establish several public-private-academic partnerships to advance AI R&D effectively while minimizing cost and ensuring privacy, transparency and accountability.

³¹⁴ Joe O'Brien, Shaun Ee, and Zoe Williams, "Deployment Corrections: An Incident Response Framework for Frontier AI Models," arXiv, September 30, 2023, 23, <http://arxiv.org/abs/2310.00328>.

³¹⁵ "FACT SHEET: Biden-Harris Administration Secures Voluntary Commitments from Leading Artificial Intelligence Companies to Manage the Risks Posed by AI," The White House, July 21, 2023, <https://perma.cc/5CG6-ZFCR>.

³¹⁶ The White House.

³¹⁷ O'Brien, Ee, and Williams, "Deployment Corrections."

³¹⁸ "How We Work," Frontier Model Forum, accessed January 25, 2024, <https://www.frontiermodelforum.org/how-we-work/>.

³¹⁹ Frontier Model Forum.

3. Law Enforcement AI Policy

The U.S. Department of Homeland Security recognizes AI as a transformative tool for enhancing national security, improving operational efficiency, and delivering superior public services. Although DHS has an overarching AI policy focusing on ensuring ethical use and safeguarding civil liberties, this thesis recommends developing specific AI policy for DHS law enforcement agencies, serving as a benchmark for others.³²⁰ This specialized policy would guide the creation of a new section within the DHS AI Policy Working Group, involving representatives from all DHS law enforcement sectors, to tailor AI tools for criminal enforcement and investigations. This improvement to the DHS AI policy will bolster law enforcement's efforts to combat all forms of transnational criminal activity, including money laundering.

The law enforcement agencies within DHS, including HSI, U.S. Secret Service, U.S. Coast Guard Investigative Service, U.S. Customs and Border Protection, and the DHS Office of Inspector General, each play unique roles in national security and public safety. Agencies like HSI and the U.S. Secret Service specifically tackle global crimes where AI's capabilities in pattern recognition and predictive analytics are crucial for detecting activities of TCOs. As these organizations increasingly employ AI to evade detection, it is imperative for DHS agencies to integrate advanced AI technologies to not only keep pace but enhance their ability to dismantle these threats effectively. A comprehensive and continuously updated AI policy will ensure that AI adoption and development are aligned with the evolving dynamics of global crime, thereby improving the efficacy of DHS's investigative endeavors.

With input from a DHS law enforcement working group – made up of agents, analysts, supervisors, executive leadership and legal advisors – DHS will develop a structured AI policy to enhance investigations. The existing HSI Innovation Lab will serve as the AI development hub for DHS law enforcement agencies, leveraging its single digital

³²⁰ Alejandro N. Mayorkas, *Acquisition and Use of Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning Technologies by DHS Components* (Washington, DC: Department of Homeland Security, 2023), https://www.dhs.gov/sites/default/files/2023-09/23_0913_mgmt_139-06-acquisition-use-ai-technologies-dhs-components.pdf.

infrastructure, the RAVEn, which is similar Estonia's X-Road. All AI tools crafted or utilized will be centrally maintained by the Innovation Lab on RAVEn and made accessible to all DHS law enforcement agency users.

Research and development of new technology requires enormous amounts of data and technical expertise, which can be costly. To secure necessary funding, the policy will mandate regular reports on the successful application of emerging AI tools. These success stories, shared with Congress and the Treasury Executive Office of Asset Forfeiture (TEOAF), will demonstrate the practical value and secure continued investment. The development strategy will incorporate open-source, government owned, and commercially available AI technologies to enhance efficiency and reduce costs.

Engagement with private sector companies and academia, as demonstrated by Estonia and Dubai, will continue under the new law enforcement specific AI policy. This collaboration has been pivotal in fostering innovation and will remain a cornerstone of the DHS approach to AI tool development.

4. Future Tools: The Potential of AI-boosted AML Capabilities

If harnessed correctly, law enforcement could prevent TCOs and money laundering networks from capitalizing on the benefits AI tools could offer. Using the same LLM hacking instructions found on the Dark Net, law enforcement, with adequate oversight, could identify various financial institutions that would be considered as primary placement locations for money launderers. After identifying those locations, law enforcement could engage directly with them, provide informational fact sheets that were generated with AI and human collaboration, and recommend open-source AML tools recently developed through public-private partnerships between the financial sector and law enforcement communities. With the more at-risk financial institutions trained on up-to-date money laundering trends and using AI upgraded AML detection tools, the attempted structuring activity would quickly be noticed and reported to the police.

The layering process would be made more difficult after the U.S. government develops a secure digital backbone enhanced with AI, similar to e-Estonia. As business registration requests are processed, beneficial owner identities are verified by cross-

referencing known identities on the databases of the Social Security Administration and each state's Real-ID systems. Business registrations attempted with false identifications would be rejected, all data associated with the attempted registration would be automatically stored in a central fraud database and reported to law enforcement. Business registries would use AI to detect unusual patterns in business registrations, such as a high number of new businesses being registered in a short time period from the same IP address. These detected patterns would be reported to police and thwart activity conducted by real individuals. Furthermore, AI systems incorporated to the BSA database held by FinCEN can quickly identify and alert law enforcement to suspicious transaction activity.

Because virtual asset activity occurs on a public ledger, or blockchain, an AI tool could be created to actively monitor blockchains to identify suspicious patterns of rapid conversion between different virtual assets to detect layering activities. To combat the trade fraud portion of money laundering, AI tools could verify the authenticity of documents submitted to financial institutions by cross-checking trade records, invoices and shipping documents against known legitimate data sources. AI can monitor large purchases of real estate and stocks, checking those transactions with known financial behaviors of money laundering networks and identifying discrepancies in purchasing patterns that do not align with legitimate financial profiles.

By integrating these advanced AI tools, law enforcement can enhance its ability to detect, prevent and investigate sophisticated money laundering schemes. These tools provide robust mechanisms for monitoring and analyzing financial transactions, ensuring that illicit activities are identified and stopped before they can be completed. This comprehensive approach leverages AI's capabilities to secure the financial system against evolving criminal tactics.

B. NEXT STEPS FOR FUTURE RESEARCH

After conducting research for this thesis, which aims to identify how law enforcement can use AI to enhance money laundering investigations, it is evident there is a lack of peer reviewed articles on this topic. Further research should examine the adaptive strategies TCOs use to develop and incorporate AI to their money laundering activities.

The research should include qualitative analysis of the evolution of AI techniques used by TCOs and quantitative studies on the frequency and success rates of such methods. Similar research should be done on how law enforcement is creating and leveraging AI to make meaningful strides to counter money laundering. Comparative studies across different jurisdictions can provide insights into global best practices in AI application by law enforcement. Research could also explore the development of AI tools and frameworks that can be standardized for cross-border cooperation in money laundering investigations. By expanding the scope to include these areas, future research can offer a comprehensive blueprint for effectively managing AI against the sophisticated dynamics of international money laundering.

C. FINAL THOUGHTS

AI has the potential to both facilitate and combat financial crimes. This thesis illustrates how TCOs exploit AI for nefarious activities, while also outlining the possibilities for law enforcement to leverage AI in countering these crimes. It showed how sophisticated AI technologies could be used in money laundering operations, demonstrating both the challenges and strategies for deploying AI in anti-money laundering investigations. There must be a balanced approach for law enforcement to use robust AI tools to keep pace with evolving criminal tactics while maintaining strong ethical standards. Anti-money laundering efforts by law enforcement require continued innovation and strategic partnerships to enhance the effectiveness of these AI tools.

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